

Compliance at the heart of the muscle

Michael Günther^{a,e}, Kasper B. Christensen^b, Daniel F. B. Haeufle^{c,d,a}, Tobias Siebert^b, Syn Schmitt^{a,f}

^a *Computational Biophysics and Biorobotics, Institut für Modellierung and Simulation Biomechanischer Systeme, Universität Stuttgart, Nobelstraße 15, 70569 Stuttgart, Germany*

^b *Motion and Exercise Science, Institut für Sport- und Bewegungswissenschaft, Universität Stuttgart, Allmandring 28, 70569 Stuttgart, Germany*

^c *Human Robot Interaction, Institut für Technische Informatik (ZITI), Universität Heidelberg, Im Neuenheimer Feld 368, 69120 Heidelberg, Germany*

^d *Multi-level Modeling in Motor Control and Rehabilitation Robotics, Hertie-Institute for Clinical Brain Research, Eberhard-Karls-Universität, Hoppe-Seyler-Straße 3, 72076 Tübingen, Germany*

^e *Friedrich-Schiller-Universität, 07737 Jena, Germany*

^f *Stuttgart Center for Simulation Science (SC SimTech), Universität Stuttgart, Pfaffenwaldring 5a, 70569 Stuttgart, Germany*

Abstract

1 In legged terrestrial locomotion of all vertebrates, there is an everyday exposure of their leg bones to impacts. Their
2 leg muscles are suspended at the bones, consequently, their mechanical design is shaped by evolution to deal with these
3 inescapable dynamical loading situations. The mechanical dynamics occurring in the leg structures in particular,
4 shock waves travelling not only along the bones but also the muscles as a response to a leg impacting the ground,
5 has been first observed in the 1980s and described in terms of deflections of the centre of mass of a muscle relative
6 to its bony suspension; this soft tissue phenomenon was named “wobbling mass dynamics”. Beyond, such impact
7 responses should also be measurable on a smaller scale, for example, in terms of local strain signals of the muscle
8 fibres. Recently, we had performed experiments on rat muscles that were dissected, suspended to a metal frame,
9 activated, and dropped on the ground, and we had measured the strains in the fibres. In the present study, we now
10 introduce a biomechanical model of a rat gastrocnemius muscle-tendon complex (MTC) that dynamically interacts
11 with a suspending frame dropped on the ground, just like in the experiments. The MTC model is of second order
12 as it consists of an alternating sequence of point masses, which represent the muscle belly’s mass distribution, and
13 contractile elements (CEs), which are modelled as active force generators that reflect the basic mechanical element
14 structure of a cross-bridge: an (elastic) element (SE) in series to the active element (AE), and a damper in parallel
15 to each of them, the serial (SDE) and the parallel damping element (PDE). Our simulation results give surprisingly
16 unambiguous evidence that the visco-elastic deformation in the locally strained fibre material does not occur in the
17 SE but entirely in the AE. In our cross-bridge model, it is assumed that the AE in the heart of the muscle is driven
18 by electro-static repulsion, which allows to consistently explain the force-length characteristic of the AE, including
19 its slope at the point of operation of a cross-bridge, which is up to two orders of magnitude lower than the stiffness of
20 the SE reflecting passive elasticity of filaments and myosin heads. The prediction of a stereotyped distal to proximal
21 strain distribution along the belly is another major result: In the early impact response (during about 12 ms), the
22 fibres shorten in the distal part of the belly, while they lengthen in the proximal part, with amplitudes increasing
23 from the centre to the fibre terminations at the aponeuroses. Our second-order MTC model is designed for size
24 scaling, thus, suitable for allometric investigations into structure-function relations of dynamic muscle contraction.

Key words: biomechanics; muscle modelling; cross-bridge model; impact response; second-order dynamics

List of abbreviations

AE	active element (drive)
CB	cross-bridge
CE	contractile element (AE+PDE&SE+SDE; one CB or a HS)
CoM	centre of muscle (belly) mass: spatial position
CSA	cross-sectional area
DoF	degree of freedom
HS	half-sarcomere
PDE	parallel (to AE) damping element
PEE	parallel (to CE) elastic element
PM	point mass
SE	serial (to AE) (elastic) element
SDE	serial (to AE) damping element
TAC	tendon-aponeurosis complex

1. Introduction

In general, a dynamically contracting muscle, and particularly one that does work while shortening, does not only have to overcome muscle-external loads plus its internal frictional resistances but also its own mass inertia. Albeit rather scarcely though quite substantially, this basic mechanical fact has been taken into account during the last five decades in both muscle experiments and modelling. If models consider, besides length or activity properties, only velocity-dependent characteristics then they can be qualified by being of ‘first order’, and if they take their own mass inertia into account then the qualifier ‘second order’ is used; this terminology is due to the highest order of a time derivative occurring in the differential equations of a mathematical model description.

On the experimental side, it seems that the effectuality of muscle inertia has first been acknowledged in isolated fibre contractions, namely, in rapid (one side) step-in-length experiments [1]. Based on the model idea of a beam (i.e. a solid yet flexible rod of distributed mass) representing a muscle fibre, they interpreted the observed high-frequency oscillations in their force signals (around 3000 Hz with 17 mm fibres) in response to step length changes to indicate (damped) waves travelling along the fibre, to and fro between both ends clamped. Later, these experiments were picked up with an improved setup to realise the most rapid steps (completed within 0.05 ms) ever until today [2]; they confirmed both the occurrence of such oscillations and the interpretation that muscle inertia was in effect [3].

It is most appropriate to acknowledge [4] here once again that Jachen Denoth at ETH in Zürich (Switzerland) led a short conference paper [5] in the year of the latter experimental study [3], in which he first formulated his mechanical model idea, derived from observing early 1980s (analog) high-speed camera recordings of human athletes, that major volumes of soft tissue within a leg (muscle masses discernibly) were deflected from their rest positions relative to the bones as a dynamic response to the leg impacting on the ground. He suggested non-linear visco-elastic force laws for mathematically introducing the mechanical coupling of the inert soft tissue masses with their respective bony limb counterparts (e.g. the shank) into the equations of motion of the leg’s chain of limb parts. The catchy name “wobbling masses” for the soft tissue parts was invented (in fact, it was a onetime “wabbling” [5] originally) and spread via a follow-up paper [6], which set the mark by theory to quantitatively predict and establish the high general relevance of wobbling masses for validly estimating body-internal loads on the structures in and as a response to impact situations.

While the wave propagation phenomenon appears to not have been followed up since [3], the wobbling mass idea was adopted [7] in a linearised form to check by a four body model whether the characteristic time course of the normal ground reaction force component (including an “impact peak”) of a human runner can be explained; shortly after, attenuation of oscillations after leg impact were investigated [8] by using a shank model with bone and wobbling mass separated; this approach was followed-up with theoretical three- [9], four- [10, 11, 12, 13], and seven-segment model investigations [14]. Since 2000, concurrently to such wobbling mass modelling studies (further examples in [4]), some direct experimental measurements (camera or accelerometer recordings of skin-mounted markers) of soft tissue motion in the legs of humans running or jumping followed [15, 16], while it was particularly found that the strength of wobbling mass coupling to the skeleton depends on muscle activity [17, 18, 19, 20, 21]. Moreover, an estimation of energy dissipation by wobbling mass motion was performed [4] by using kinematic information from a net painted on the skin [22].

The relevance of muscle mass inertia in biological locomotion, and correspondingly second-order muscle modelling for potentially understanding the functional impact of mass, has been proved by convincingly suggesting that the characteristic absolute maximum value of the allometry of maximum running speed across all legged species on earth can be explained by the inertia of crucial leg muscles [23]. Likewise, inert mass, be it interpreted as that of the body or a muscle, is a core part of a very recent theory [24, 25, 26] on two basic physical, i.e. inescapable, limits for muscles to do work. This theory allows novel reflections on how and why body designs of animals emerged under various functional requirements for their locomotion solutions, which, in turn, are due to movement strategies necessary to exploit their ecological niches. The limitation of contraction performance of an isolated muscle by the muscle’s own mass inertia had already been indicated several years before [27] by means of a simulation analysis. There, it had been found that the limit set by a sarcomere’s cross-bridge cycling properties to contraction velocity was interfered with by increasing overall muscle mass, i.e. with increasing size of an animal. Based on this combination of distributed masses of a muscle interacting with classical Hill-type [28] (phenomenological, steady-state, first-order) contractile properties, further limiting consequences by muscle inertia for diverse muscle performance indicators have been carved out in a sequence of papers, from [29] via e.g. [30, 31] to [32]. Given the timeline of research on muscle inertia and its hesitant implementation in models of muscle contraction described thus far, it is indeed breath-taking that already in 1997 an outstanding theoretical work [33] introducing a spatially distributed second-order muscle model had quantitatively pinpointed the impact of distributed muscle mass along a squid tentacle on its explosive extension for prey hunting.

83 As final note in this introductory attempt of a survey of research on the functionality of muscle inertia in biological
84 movement, it should be annotated that conducting spectral analyses of observed movements is a useful window to
85 the passive and active forces having acted during the movement. This is because the observed frequencies tell about
86 the tissue stiffnesses *in relation to* the mass distribution of and around them. The other way round, knowing the
87 mass distribution generally allows inferring passive material stiffnesses as well as muscle activities. A very recent
88 study [34] gave an example of this methodical approach by identifying the dependency of some eigenfrequencies of
89 rat muscle on the local stiffness distribution along it.

90 Two other recent experimental studies [35, 36] stepped beyond skin-covered observations of soft tissue excursions,
91 with directly observing wobbling mass motion across the surfaces of isolated but intact rat muscles. The muscles
92 were dissected together with their distal and proximal tendon-aponeuroses complexes, suspended by bony remainders
93 on the tendons to a metal frame, and activated repeatedly while simultaneously dropping the frame on the ground.
94 In [36], the averaged (over about half of the belly length) longitudinal strain amplitudes of muscle fibre material
95 as a response to an impact along the fibre direction could be well explained by a zero-order (i.e. only force-length
96 relations) non-linear two-element model, which reflected the non-dissipative parts of the mechanical structure of a
97 cross-bridge (CB) scaled to a half-sarcomere (HS): the ‘active element’ (AE) and the ‘serial element’ (SE) arranged in
98 series to the AE. The two dissipative (damping) parts of the complete CB model had been neglected in that analysis
99 of just the amplitudes: the ‘parallel damping element’ (PDE), and the ‘serial damping element’ (SDE) arranged in
100 parallel and in series to the AE, respectively. This result was promising, first, because the complete CB model had
101 been validated beforehand [37] against rapid step-in-length and step-in-force experiments [38, 39, 40] in single fibres;
102 and, second, its combination of two CB-based force-length relations had proved superior in the strain analysis [36],
103 in terms of consistency and explanatory power, to another purely elastic (i.e. zero-order) HS model that had been
104 formulated in [41] based on experiments applying 4000 Hz oscillations to single fibres.

105 With the point of departure outlined, our present study aimed at probing by direct dynamics computer simulations
106 whether a mechanical model of a finite number of macroscopic sub-regions of a muscle belly (the assembly of muscle
107 fibres), which dynamically interact with the belly mass distributed between these sub-regions (each mass portion
108 modelled as a point mass, PM), can explain the measured amplitudes and timings of local strains in the belly as
109 a response to an impact of physiological intensity. In this, the modelled active fibre force of a belly’s sub-region is
110 generated by an up-scaled model of a HS that in itself is conceived of as being assembled from one to one hundred
111 CBs, of which each one models the same arrangement of four ‘rheological’ elements (termed ‘contractile element’,
112 CE) that represent the structural parts and mechanical properties a real CB is made of [37]. This CB-based CE
113 model is of first order, while the alternating sequence of the belly’s sub-regions (CEs) and PMs yields a mechanical
114 model of second order. With each a tendon-aponeurosis complex (TAC) connected distally and proximally to the
115 whole belly model, the resulting mechanical model of the muscle-tendon complex (MTC), which is likewise of second
116 order due to the muscle belly’s mass inertia taken into account, is simulated while being exposed to the same side
117 and boundary conditions as in our former impact experiments [35, 36]: Namely, the model analogues of the bony
118 insertions’s remainders of the totally intact TACs (end points of visco-elastic elements) were clamped to the model
119 frame (connecting points on a rigid body), all CEs of the belly model were equally activated (giving the number of
120 CBs in a HS as a model input), and the model frame was dropped and then impacted, after a free fall subject to
121 gravity, the ground-fixed visco-elastic cushion element that modelled the frame-ground force interaction.

122 2. Model formulation

123 The mechanical structure of the model part that represents the entirety of actively contracting muscle fibres (the
124 belly) within the suspended MTC (here, of a rat’s *m. gastrocnemius*, GAS) replicates what we have introduced in
125 [27] (see right side of Fig. 1): an alternating sequence of a finite number of point masses (PMs: red-filled circles) and
126 contractile elements (CEs: blue-magenta sketches symbolising cross-bridges, CBs). Compared to [27], this belly part
127 is enhanced by two essential features: (i) each a proximal and a distal tendon(-aponeurosis) model part is attached
128 to the modelled belly’s ends (to both outermost PMs, see again Fig. 1), in terms of mass-less non-linear visco-
129 elastic elements (tendon-aponeuroses complexes, TACs: TAC,d and TAC,p, ‘d’ and ‘p’ for ‘distal’ and ‘proximal’,
130 respectively, depicted as yellow springs with remainders of the tendons’ bony insertion parts clamped to the frame),
131 and (ii) the Hill-type CEs in [27], each characterised by a phenomenological (bell-curve-shaped) force-length and
132 (hyperbolic) force-velocity relation, are replaced by CEs that represent CB-structure-based force-deformation and
133 (force-dependent) damping properties, as introduced in [37]. All these biomechanical CB properties have been
134 condensed into one ordinary first-order differential equation [37, eq. 22] for each CE,i in terms of the rate of length

change $\dot{L}_{SE,i}(L_{CE,i}, \dot{L}_{CE,i}, L_{SE,i}, CB \text{ parameters})$ of the serial element (SE) part of the CB-based CE model [37, figs. 2,3; eq. 7]. This allows the implementation of the CB-based CE model in a straight-forward way into the second-order system of the mechanical equations of motion of the PMs: Both the CEs' and the TACs' forces, $F_{CE,i} = F_{CE,i}(u_{AE}, L_{CE,i}, \dot{L}_{CE,i}, L_{SE,i}, \dot{L}_{SE,i}, CB \text{ parameters})$ and $F_{TAC,d|p} = F_{TAC,d|p}(L_{TAC,d|p}, \dot{L}_{TAC,d|p}, TAC \text{ parameters})$, respectively, only depend on the mechanical frame-and-PMs system's states (from their positions and velocities: the CEs' lengths and their rates), and in the case of a CE, also on its own state variable (the SE length) and muscle activity (u_{AE}), as well as all elements (CEs and TACs) on the parameters of their respective force characteristics. In the following, we outline the mechanical properties of the belly mass distribution, the TACs, as well as the CB-structure-based CEs, and explain the parametrisation that allows size scaling of the MTC and taking muscle activity into account. Finally, the initial conditions chosen for simulating the activated MTC to be dropped on the ground while being suspended in the rigid frame (see again Fig. 1) are given, and the numerical parameters for rigid-body simulations using the biomechanical frame-and-MTC model.

2.1. Mass distribution of the belly, and the force coupling within the MTC and to its suspending frame: the model's mechanical equations of motion

We simulated the impact response of a frame-suspended rat GAS MTC, with its mass $\mathcal{M} = 2 \text{ g}$ entirely attributed to the belly and spread out along a sequence of $n_{CE} + 1 = 25$ PMs (right-most chain of red dots in Fig. 1) connected (force-coupled) by $n_{CE} = 24$ CEs. In case of a homogeneous mass distribution within the belly, each PM has a mass of $\mathcal{M}_i = 0.08 \text{ g}$. Here, we chose some inhomogeneous distribution (Fig. 2) as a model default to approximate the tapered and moderately asymmetrical shape of the GAS belly. Accordingly, the model belly's CoM is positioned slightly distally to the anatomical centre of the belly, the latter located half the way from the insertion of the distal tendon, $y < 0$, to that of the proximal one, $y > 0$.

Using 't' as the symbol for time, the system of equations of motion of the model belly—to be integrated with the parameter values of all force laws, the initial conditions (positions and velocities) of all PMs, and the initial internal lengths of the CEs' SEs (see further below) given—is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{M}_i \cdot \ddot{y}_i(t) &= -\mathcal{M}_i \cdot g + F_{CE,i}(t) + F_{PEE,i}(t) - F_{TAC,d}(t) && \text{if } i = 1 \\ \mathcal{M}_i \cdot \ddot{y}_i(t) &= -\mathcal{M}_i \cdot g + F_{CE,i}(t) + F_{PEE,i}(t) - F_{CE,i-1}(t) - F_{PEE,i-1}(t) && \text{if } 2 \leq i \leq n_{CE} \\ \mathcal{M}_i \cdot \ddot{y}_i(t) &= -\mathcal{M}_i \cdot g - F_{CE,i-1}(t) - F_{PEE,i-1}(t) + F_{TAC,p}(t) && \text{if } i = n_{CE} + 1 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Eqs. (1) reflect Newton's second law implemented for any PM (each single one abbreviated as PM,i). Accordingly, the double dots ' ' above y denote its second time derivative (y acceleration), $g > 0$ the absolute value of the gravitational acceleration (on earth: $g = 9.81 \text{ s}^{-2}\text{m}$), and $1 \leq i \leq n_{CE} + 1$ the index of both PM,i ($i = 1$ for the most distal one) and CE,i, the latter being located and pulling (in the common case $F_{CE,i} > 0$ of its force generation) proximally on the PM with the same i value (i.e. PM,i). The CE forces $F_{CE,i}(t)$ depend on the model representation of muscle 'activity', the ratio

$$u_{AE} = \frac{n_{hs,cb}}{n_{hs,cbmax}} \quad (2)$$

of the actual number $n_{hs,cb}$ of CBs in a half-sarcomere (HS) and their maximum $n_{hs,cbmax} = 100$, with $1 \leq n_{hs,cb} \leq n_{hs,cbmax}$ or $0.01 \leq u_{AE} \leq 1$, correspondingly. Activity u_{AE} is a freely chosen model input number, a *constant* value assigned before simulation. As with the CE forces $F_{CE,i}$, the common case of a TAC generating a positive force $F_{TAC,j} > 0$ means that this TAC (the two yellow, curly strings in Fig. 1: TAC,d below and TAC,p above the PM sequence) pulls on the PM connected to it. The distal and the proximal model TACs (massless visco-elastic force elements) then connect the mass distribution of the model belly, the PM sequence, to a rigid body, the frame (grey part in Fig. 1). Moreover, we have additionally implemented a linear spring named 'parallel elastic element' (PEE,i), which responds with a (pulling) force

$$F_{PEE,i}(L_{AE,i}) = K_{PEE,i} \cdot (L_{AE,i} - L_{PEE,i,0}) \quad (3)$$

in parallel to CE,i, if the PEE,i's rest length

$$L_{PEE,i,0} = L_{CE,opt,i} + \mathcal{L}_{PEE} \cdot L_{CE,ref,i} \quad (4)$$

is exceeded, with

$$K_{PEE,i} = \mathcal{C}_{PEE} \cdot K_{AE,ref,max,i} \quad (5)$$

175 being the PEE,*i*'s stiffness. The parameters $L_{AE,ref,i}$, $L_{CE,ref,i} = L_{AE,ref,i} + L_{SE,ref,i}$, and $K_{AE,ref,max,i}$, identical for
176 each PEE,*i*, are gained by scaling from CB via HS to CE,*i* level by the number $n_{L,hs,i} = \frac{L_{CE,opt}}{L_{hs,ref}}$ of HSs in series within
177 one CE,*i*, and, in case of the stiffness $K_{AE,ref,max,i}$, by the *maximum* number $n_{CSA,cbmax}$ (i.e., for the time being,
178 $K_{PEE,i}$ independent of activity u_{AE} !) of CBs acting in parallel in a CE,*i*, i.e. in the cross-sectional area (CSA) of the
179 belly: $L_{AE,ref,i} = n_{L,hs,i} \cdot L_{AE,cb,ref}$, $L_{SE,ref,i} = n_{L,hs,i} \cdot L_{SE,hs,cbmax}$, and $K_{AE,ref,max,i} = \frac{u_{AE} \cdot n_{CSA,cbmax}}{n_{L,hs,i}} \cdot K_{AE,cb,ref}$;
180 the latter $K_{AE,cb,ref}$ is the slope of the force-length relation of a CB at its working point $F_{AE,cb}(L_{AE,cb,ref}) = F_{cb,ref}$
181 (see Eq. (20) in Sec. 2.4 further below). All of these model parameter values can be found in Table 1, the independent
182 ones printed in **bold** font; naturally, most of them were fixed for all present simulations, yet some in the list are
183 default values that have been varied, as e.g. \mathcal{C}_{PEE} , i.e. the PEE,*i*'s stiffness.

184 The frame-MTC system (frame mass: \mathcal{M}_{fra}) drops subjected to gravity acting along the y -axis, while frictionless
185 railing is assumed (see grey protrusions from the frame gripping and sliding on the vertical rail part of the black
186 stand on the left side of Fig. 1). In our two-dimensional simulation code, all PMs, and thus the overall CoM
187 of the MTC (y_{MTC}), as well as that of the frame (y_{fra}) align at the same x position that also the contact point
188 between frame and ground is located at. Therefore, the whole system dynamics of frame and PMs occur actually
189 along only one dimension, y , and no torques play a role (thus, the frame's moment of inertia is irrelevant in our
190 simulations). Accordingly, the frame moves, mutually coupled to the MTC by the TAC forces acting at $y_{TAC,d}(t) =$
191 $y_{fra}(t) - \frac{L_{CE,opt}}{2} - L_{TAC,d,0}$ ($F_{TAC,d}$) and $y_{TAC,p}(t) = y_{fra}(t) + \frac{L_{CE,opt}}{2} + L_{TAC,p,0}$ ($F_{TAC,p}$), subjected to the equation
192 of motion

$$\mathcal{M}_{fra} \cdot \ddot{y}_{fra}(t) = -\mathcal{M}_{fra} \cdot g - F_{TAC,p}(t) + F_{TAC,d}(t) + F_{fra}(t) \quad , \quad (6)$$

193 with the ground contact force F_{fra} acting at $y_{fra,bot}(t) = y_{fra}(t) - \frac{H_{fra}}{2}$ (frame height: $H_{fra} = L_{CE,opt} + L_{TAC,d,0} +$
194 $L_{TAC,p,0} = constant$). This implies the thickness of the model frame being zero and the y -position of the frame's
195 only contact point with the ground being simply identified with the distal TAC attachment point. Further, and also
196 implied with $H_{fra} = constant$, the MTC length $L_{MTC}(t) = y_{TAC,p}(t) - y_{TAC,d}(t)$ generally equals the frame height
197 H_{fra} in all our simulations here, meaning that the MTC is held in isometric condition and close to its optimal length
198 $L_{MTC}(t) = H_{fra} \approx L_{MTC,opt}$ at any activity level (u_{AE}); the symbols $y_{TAC,d}$ and $y_{TAC,p}$ are the positions of the
199 modelled distal and proximal, respectively, TACs' fixation points to the model frame (representing each the tendon
200 insertion into its bony remainder, which is clamped to the frame).

201 The force law that determines the force response $F_{fra}(t)$ (the ground reaction force acting on the frame) to
202 deformation of the cushion material when the bottom of the frame contacts the cushion, the latter being spread out
203 on the ground below the frame (visualised at right, bottom in Fig. 1 by the green area), is modelled as

$$F_{fra}(y_{fra,bot}, \dot{y}_{fra,bot}) = -K_{cush} \cdot (y_{fra,bot} - y_{cush,top}) \cdot (1 + \delta_{cush} \cdot \dot{y}_{fra,bot}) \quad , \quad (7)$$

204 with $y_{cush,top} = constant$, $K_{cush} = 4000.0 \text{ N m}^{-1}$, and $\delta_{cush} = \frac{1}{3} \text{ s m}^{-1}$. Given the frame mass $\mathcal{M}_{fra} = 52 \text{ g}$, the
205 eigenfrequency of the frame-cushion system is about 44 Hz.

206 A TAC's non-linear visco-elastic coupling force

$$F_{TAC}(L_{TAC}, \dot{L}_{TAC}) = F_{TAC,elas}(L_{TAC}) + F_{TAC,diss}(L_{TAC}, \dot{L}_{TAC}) \quad (8)$$

207 is modelled (in full analogy to [42]) as the sum of an elastic

$$F_{TAC,elas}(L_{TAC}) = \begin{cases} 0 & , L_{TAC} < L_{TAC,0} \\ C_{TAC,nl} \cdot (L_{TAC} - L_{TAC,0})^{\nu_{TAC}} & , L_{TAC} < L_{TAC,nll} \\ \Delta F_{TAC,0} + K_{TAC} \cdot (L_{TAC} - L_{TAC,nll}) & , L_{TAC} \geq L_{TAC,nll} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

208 and a dissipative

$$F_{TAC,diss}(L_{TAC}, \dot{L}_{TAC}) = D_{TAC,max} \cdot \left((1 - R_{TAC}) \cdot \frac{F_{TAC,elas}(L_{TAC})}{F_{max}} + R_{TAC} \right) \cdot \dot{L}_{TAC} \quad (10)$$

209 contribution. The fundamental macroscopic force scaling MTC parameter F_{max} (the maximum isometric force of the
210 muscle belly at full activity: $u_{AE} = 1$) is used in our MTC model to guarantee proper force scaling of CE and TAC
211 forces at once. The four independent elastic TAC model parameters are $L_{TAC,0}$ (rest length), f_{TAC} (determining force

$\Delta F_{TAC,0}$ at non-linear-linear transition), $\Delta U_{TAC,nll}$ (strain to non-linear-linear transition), and $\Delta U_{TAC,l}$ (strain in the elastic region if $\Delta F_{TAC,0}$ acts on top of $\Delta F_{TAC,0}$; together: determining stiffness); the following dependent parameters are introduced as symbols supporting a concise formulation of the elastic force law: $\Delta F_{TAC,0} = f_{TAC} \cdot F_{max}$ (force $\Delta F_{TAC,0}$ at non-linear-linear transition), $L_{TAC,nll} = (1 + \Delta U_{nll}) \cdot L_{TAC,0}$ (length of non-linear-linear transition), $C_{TAC,nl} = \frac{\Delta F_{TAC,0}}{(\Delta U_{nll} \cdot L_{TAC,0}^{\nu_{TAC}})}$ (coefficient of non-linear region), $\nu_{TAC} = \frac{\Delta U_{TAC,nll}}{\Delta U_{TAC,l}}$ (exponent of non-linear region), and $K_{TAC} = \frac{dF_{TAC,0}}{\Delta U_{TAC,l} \cdot L_{TAC,0}}$ (stiffness in the elastic region). There are only two independent dissipative parameters: a characteristic time \mathcal{T} that linearly scales the maximum dissipation coefficient $D_{TAC,max} = \frac{F_{max} \cdot \mathcal{T}_{TAC}}{L_{TAC,0}}$ (besides automatic MTC length and force scaling by $L_{TAC,0}$ and F_{max}), and the dimensionless multiplier R_{TAC} that fixes a remainder $R_{TAC} \cdot D_{TAC,max}$ of the damping coefficient that is independent of $F_{TAC,elast}$. All parameters and their chosen values are compiled in the bottom part of Table 1.

2.2. Connecting the PMs: essential cross-bridge (CB) structure transferred to a mechanical ('rheological') element arrangement (the CE)

Fig. 3 depicts the essential physico-geometrical structure of a CB (top-left): the catalytic domain (CD) attached to actin, the light chain domain (LCD) pivoting around some point [43, 44] in or on the CD, the LCD lever arm's active drive (AE'; hypothesised dipole [45] or Coulomb [46, 47, 37] repulsion, the latter symbolised by a "piston in a cylinder" [46]), and serial compliances in green and gold, respectively. Two characteristic CB and HS configurations in terms of their positional states (LCD angle, AE' position, and distance between M-line and Z-disc, i.e. HS length) are also distinguished: assumed states of start and end of a CB work stroke. In the state 'start of work stroke', a characteristic reference force $F_{cb,ref}$ (see the AE force-length relation $F_{AE,cb}(L_{AE,cb})$ in the panel bottom-right, the upper part at $L_{AE,cb} = 7$ nm) acts between M-line and Z-disc, and drives both ends of a HS to approach each other (pull); (loaded) elastic parts are coloured in green. In our CB model (Fig. 3, top-right), which constitutes the CE on the most microscopic level taken into account, a serial element (SE) lumps the structural elasticities of all (CB and filament) parts in series to the active drive AE' in a CB, namely, both the elastic compliances within each CB itself (e.g. a bending LCD, and stretch elasticity of the S2 part) and those within the HS (elasticities of myosin and actin filaments the CB is immediately attached to, including each their respective M-line and Z-disc). A linear spring models the characteristic SE force-length relation $F_{SE,hs}(L_{SE,hs})$ of a HS, which is depicted in the lower part of the panel bottom-right; (maximally) loaded with $F_{SE,hs} = n_{hs,cbmax} \cdot F_{cb,ref}$, the HS's SE responds with a deformation of $L_{SE,cb} = 4$ nm from its rest position at $L_{AE,cb} = 0$ nm. The panel depicts the force-length relation of one 'representative' CB, as it plots on the vertical axis the HS force generated by the $n_{hs,cbmax}$ (in our model: 100) CBs in a HS, divided by their number to directly compare the effect of external HS load changes on length changes in the SE and AE parts of *each single* CB in the HS. Due to the mechanical structure of CBs in HS acting in parallel, yet on the filament parts in series, the HS stiffness $K_{SE,hs}$ does generally depend (non-linearly: Fig. 4) on the number $n_{hs,cb}$ of CBs in the HS (i.e. activity u_{AE} , Eq. 2), and so does $F_{SE,hs}(L_{SE,hs}, u_{AE})$ accordingly. In a CB's state 'end of work stroke', AE force is zero ($F_{AE,cb}(L_{AE,cb}) = 0$ at $L_{AE,cb} = 0$ nm), and, assuming damping forces are low to insignificant, both the SE part of the CB alone and that of the filament are entirely unloaded ($F_{SE,hs}(L_{SE,hs} = 0, u_{AE}) = 0$), as the elastic parts of *all* CBs are synchronously unloaded because in our present impact response model we assume that all CBs within one of the n_{CE} modelled CE_i regions of the belly (i.e. between two adjacent PMs) are in the same state: all their LCDs are unbent, and their S2 'springs' as well as all other filament parts are at their rest positions (Fig. 1, top-left: elastic parts are yellow) at the 'end of work stroke'. Illustrating only one exemplary CB in this top-left panel serves to enhance the clarity of the sketch, and the HS length is consequently drawn out of scale, much too short as compared to the myosin-actin spacing.

The transfer of the CB structure to our CE model with a mechanically equivalent arrangement of actively force-generating (AE' and AE, respectively) and passively force-transmitting (SE, SDE, PDE) elements (a 'rheological' model of a CB) is illustrated for the state 'start of work stroke' top-right, and again bottom-left for a state approaching 'end of work stroke' ('end' is mathematically characterised in our model by $L_{AE,cb} = L_{AE,hs} = L_{SE,hs} = 0$ or more macroscopically $L_{AE,i} = L_{SE,i} = 0$, respectively, which cannot reasonably be reflected in an illustration of structures). Here, SDE and PDE abbreviate the CE model's damping elements in parallel to SE and AE', respectively; being heat generators, they represent energy dissipation that unavoidably accompanies any deformation in nature, one separately for each mode of deformation possible in the CE model (AE' or AE, respectively, and SE).

2.3. Connecting the PMs: the mechanical CB-CE model for generating active muscle force, its basic equations

A CE can be identified on each of the four size scales (structural levels) taken into account by our belly model. As the most basic model idea, all CBs in all HSs of one macroscopic belly part CE_i are conceived to be in one and the

264 same length-velocity-activity state. This assumption can be applied here because only the dynamic impact response
265 of the MTC within a few milliseconds is mechanically analysed in this study (attachment-detachment-reattachment
266 dynamics are not considered). The four distinct levels (i)-(iv), together with some further basic model assumptions,
267 are (i) On the CB level, the kinematic constraint or length equation, respectively, writes: $L_{CE,cb} = L_{AE,cb} + L_{SE,cb}$,
268 i.e. there is one CE-internal length DoF, (here $L_{SE,cb}$, with L_{CE} assumed to be ultimately *given* by mechanical states
269 of adjacent muscle masses). (ii) On the HS level, $L_{CE,hs} = L_{hs} = L_{hs,ref} + L_{CE,cb}$ applies, with $L_{hs,ref} = \text{constant}$
270 (i.e. independent of time). As a note, all $n_{hs,cb}$ ($= \text{constant}$) CBs—the fraction $u_{AE} = \frac{n_{hs,cb}}{n_{hs,cbmax}}$ of its maximum
271 value $n_{hs,cbmax} = 100$ is termed muscle *activity*, which is treated as a basic input to our present model—in all HSs
272 of one macroscopic CE,*i*, (see (iii) next) are in the *same* length $L_{AE,cb,i} = \frac{L_{AE,i}}{n_{L,hs,i}}$ (and velocity) state (see Fig. 5);
273 likewise, $L_{SE,cb,i} = \frac{L_{SE,i}}{n_{L,hs,i}}$ applies to the CE,*i*-internal state $L_{SE,i}$. (iii) On the level of one of the $n_{CE} = 24$ CEs (i.e.
274 CE,*i* with $1 \leq i \leq n_{CE}$) that connect each two of the serially arranged $n_{CE} + 1 = 25$ PMs representing the muscle
275 belly's inertia, each a CE,*i*'s length $L_{CE,i}$ is *known* to its corresponding CB-CE model dynamics (see Eq. (38) further
276 below) when time integrating these n_{CE} equations of CB-CE contraction dynamics (Eq. (38)) in parallel with the
277 frame's (Eq. (6)) and all $n_{CE} + 1$ PMs' (Eq. (1)) mechanical equations of motion. Eventually, (iv) on the level of the
278 overall macroscopic MTC, the belly with its length $L_{CE} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_{CE}} L_{CE,i}$ is parametrised by its maximum fully active
279 ($n_{hs,cb} = n_{hs,cbmax}$) isometric force $F_{max} = 30$ N generated at its reference length $L_{CE,opt} = 3.3$ cm, which are basic
280 muscle model input parameters, just like $n_{CE} = 24$, $n_{hs,cbmax} = 100$, and $1 \leq n_{hs,cb} \leq n_{hs,cbmax}$.

281 At any point in time t in ongoing coupled gravity-MTC-frame-ground dynamics, a CE,*i*'s length $L_{CE,i}(t)$ and
282 length rate $\dot{L}_{CE,i}(t)$ are given by solely the mechanical state of the PMs adjacent to a CE,*i*. Mathematically spoken,
283 they constitute a rheonomic constraint

$$L_{CE,i} = \lambda \cdot L_{AE',i} + L_{SE,i} = L_{AE,i} + L_{SE,i}, \text{ therefore also} \quad (11)$$

$$\dot{L}_{CE,i} = \lambda \cdot \dot{L}_{AE',i} + \dot{L}_{SE,i} = \dot{L}_{AE,i} + \dot{L}_{SE,i} \quad (12)$$

284 to the CE,*i*'s temporal changes in its internal length DoF (either $L_{AE,i}$ or $L_{SE,i}$). For legibility reasons of the
285 mathematical description, we have omitted the time-dependency symbol '(*t*)' of all lengths in Eqs. (11,12), and also
286 of the forces in Eqs. (13,14) further below. Here (look at Fig. 3, top-left again), $\lambda = 22$ is the lever arm ratio for
287 gearing a change in position $\Delta L_{AE'}$ of the proposed Coulomb repulsion drive AE' within the CB, the 'piston', to
288 the corresponding shift ΔL_{AE} of the endpoint of the (notionally always unbent) cross-bridge lever being effective
289 between myosin and actin, i.e. between M-line and Z-disc. Besides the length changes of the two serially arranged
290 elements, AE and SE, being subjected to this *kinematic constraint* (Eq. (11)), the force

$$F_{CE,i} = F_{AE,i}(L_{AE,i}) + F_{PDE,i}(L_{AE,i}, \dot{L}_{AE,i}) = F_{SE,i}(L_{SE,i}) + F_{SDE,i}(L_{SE,i}, \dot{L}_{SE,i}) \quad (13)$$

$$= F_{AE,i}(L_{AE,i}) + D_{PDE,i}(F_{SE,i}(L_{SE,i}), F_{AE,i}(L_{AE,i})) \cdot \frac{\dot{L}_{AE,i}}{\lambda} = F_{SE,i}(L_{SE,i}) + D_{SDE,i}(F_{SE,i}(L_{SE,i})) \cdot \dot{L}_{SE,i} \quad (14)$$

291 generation of their coupled arrangement, i.e. of the CE,*i* including its respective damping 'brakes' PDE and SDE, is
292 subjected to Newton's third law, a *force equilibrium* (Eq. (13)) to be fulfilled by the four CB model elements (AE,
293 SE, PDE, and SDE) at the CE,*i*-internal connection point of AE&PDE and SE&SDE; note that, again for legibility
294 reasons, we have omitted symbolising all forces' ($F_{AE,i}$, $F_{SE,i}$, $F_{PDE,i}$, and $F_{SDE,i}$) parametric dependencies on
295 activity u_{AE} in Eqs. (13,14), just like time t dependency of lengths. This connection point is the CE,*i*-internal DoF
296 that comes in addition to the mechanical DoFs of the PM chain and the frame. That is, each CE,*i* ($i = 1, \dots, n_{CE}$)
297 adds one variable (here, we chose $L_{SE,i}$) to describe the time-dependent state of the overall MTC system. The
298 force $F_{CE,i}$ generated by the CE,*i* depends explicitly on the lengths and length rates of the two serially arranged
299 elements, AE and SE, due to the mechanical properties (force laws, see below; length dependencies in particular:
300 Fig. 3, bottom-right) of all four CB model elements (AE, SE, PDE, and SDE); $F_{CE,i}$ (re-)acts on both adjacent PMs
301 at any time t , and, with this, impacts their states, positions and velocities, in interaction with gravity and the other
302 CE,*i*'s forces acting within the PM chain. Together, the set of Eqs. (11,12,13) constitutes the contraction dynamics
303 of the CB model introduced in [37] and used here (see again Fig. 3: the CB structural sketch, top-left, as well as its
304 transfer to a mechanically equivalent element arrangement, top-right), which is then scaled (according to Sec. 2.6) to
305 the macroscopic level of a CE,*i* (see Eq. (38)).

2.4. Connecting the PMs: the characteristic relations (force laws) of the mechanical elements within the CB-CE model

2.4.1. Damping (PDE and SDE): force-velocity relations

In [37], on the one hand, steady-state solutions of Eqs. (11,12,13,14) had been analysed, and, on the other hand, solutions reflecting fibre contraction responses to rapid steps in length or force. In particular, at greater step amplitudes, both a CB's AE and its SE go through their full length and force ranges, and one of the main findings in [37] was that experimental and CB model simulation results by far matched best with assuming the PDE damping coefficient $D_{PDE,cb}$ to be simply a scaled (essentially, by parameter κ_d , Eq. (17)) version of the SDE coefficient (see [37, eqs. 31,32])

$$D_{SDE,cb}(F_{SE,cb}) = d_{def,cb}(F_{SE,cb}) = D_{def,max,cb} \cdot \left((1 - R_{def}) \cdot \frac{F_{SE,cb}}{F_{cb,ref}} + R_{def} \right) \quad , \quad (15)$$

which provides the SDE force

$$\begin{aligned} F_{SDE,i}(L_{SE,i}, \dot{L}_{SE,i}, u_{AE}) &= D_{SDE,i}(F_{SE,i}(L_{SE,i}, u_{AE})) \cdot \dot{L}_{SE,i} \\ &= d_{def,i}(F_{SE,i}(L_{SE,i}, u_{AE})) \cdot \dot{L}_{SE,i} \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

in Eq. (13); for scaling lengths, forces (e.g. $F_{cb,ref}$ to $F_{max,i} = F_{max}$), damping coefficients (e.g. $D_{def,max,cb}$ to $D_{def,max,i}$), and stiffnesses from CB via HS to CE,i: see Sec. 2.6.

However, in stark contrast to rapid step responses, it turns out that the deformations of an SE in response to an impact at physiological intensity level, as simulated here, are, in fact, minuscule as compared to deformations of the AE, the heart of the muscle's drive. This is because the stiffness ratio between AE and SE in a CB or HS, respectively, is already well known from these rapid step experiments (in length or force; SE: see [37, 38, 39, 40, 46]; AE: see [37, 46]), at least at full activity ($u_{AE} = 1$); and our more recent analyses [36, 35] have exactly confirmed this stiffness ratio being vital to explain strain responses of the fibre material in response to impacts, even down to much lower activities. The crucial stiffness values are given in Table 2 (see e.g. at the level of a CE,i): even at an activity as low as $u_{AE} = 0.1$, $K_{SE,i} = K_{SE,med,i} = 1.5 \cdot 10^6 \text{ Nm}^{-1}$ is more than an order of magnitude higher than $K_{AE,ref,max,i} = 9.52 \cdot 10^4 \text{ Nm}^{-1}$, the slope of the force-length relation $F_{AE,cb}(L_{AE,cb})$ at the common working point of a cross-bridge, a CB's reference state, conceivably occupied on average in isometric condition. As a consequence, $F_{SDE,i}$ practically vanishes in Eq. (13) or Eq. (14), respectively, in impact responses. In them, $F_{CE,i} \approx F_{AE,i} \approx F_{SE,i}$ always applies, as $F_{PDE,i}$ values are generally more than an order of magnitude lower than the isometric pre-load of the MTC. Hence, this experimental situation cannot distinguish between the two so far theoretically hypothesised $D_{PDE,i}$ contributions, both will be very close to constant during the impact response, and both go in proportion to activity u_{AE} . Therefore, in the present 'wobbling mass' model we stuck to what was found in rapid step conditions, namely, to performing our impact simulations by solely taking the $F_{SE,i}$ -dependent contribution to the PDE coefficient $D_{PDE,i}$ [37, eqs. 32,33] for modelling the PDE force

$$\begin{aligned} F_{PDE,i}(L_{SE,i}, \dot{L}_{AE,i}, u_{AE}) &= D_{PDE,i}(F_{SE}(L_{SE,i}, u_{AE})) \cdot \frac{\dot{L}_{AE,i}}{\lambda} \\ &= \kappa_d \cdot \lambda \cdot d_{def,i}(F_{SE,i}(L_{SE,i}, u_{AE})) \cdot \frac{\dot{L}_{AE,i}}{\lambda} \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

into account (for d_{def} definition, see again Eq. (15) above), which formally simplifies Eq. (14) ($D_{PDE,i}$ independent of $F_{AE,i}$).

The value $D_{def,max,cb} = 7.5 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ Nsm}^{-1}$ of the maximum SDE coefficient found in [37] in adjustment to rapid step in length or force experiments would have been by a factor of about 75 too high as compared to what has been inferred from experimental data on impacts (see [36, fig. 2d]). From the latter analysis, a maximum value of $D_{def,max,cb} \approx 9 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ Nsm}^{-1}$ could be estimated if the damping within the whole CB according to [36] ($\frac{D_{hs,exp,u_{AE}=1}}{n_{hs,cbmax}} \approx 2 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ Nsm}^{-1}$) were to be attributed to solely the $F_{SE,cb}$ -dependent $D_{PDE,cb}$ contribution $\frac{\kappa_d \cdot \lambda \cdot D_{def,max,cb}}{\lambda} = \kappa_d \cdot D_{def,max,cb}$, i.e. damping all right solely due to length changes of the AE, but its strength in proportion to the SE force (mechanical idea: some kind of 'joint friction' [37, p. 160, left, bottom]). In fact, by choosing about half of this first guess value from [36, fig. 2d], i.e. $D_{def,max,cb} \approx 4 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ Nsm}^{-1}$, our simulations yielded very good matches to measured local strain amplitudes.

We also simply tested numerically the just explained idea of “indistinguishability in impact responses” of an F_{SE} -dependent D_{PDE} contribution via $d_{def}(F_{SE})$ from an F_{AE} -dependent one via [37, eqs. 33,34], namely, by substituting

$$D_{PDE,i} = d_{hyd,i}(F_{AE,i}, u_{AE}) = D_{hyd,max,i} \cdot \frac{F_{AE,i}(L_{AE,i}, u_{AE})}{F_{max}} \quad (18)$$

instead of $D_{PDE,i} = D_{PDE,i}(F_{SE}(L_{SE,i}, u_{AE}))$ into Eq. (17). Indistinguishability was perfectly demonstrable (apart from numerical subtleties) by multiplying $D_{def,max,cb}$ with $\kappa_d \cdot \lambda$, which converts to an equivalent $D_{hyd,max,cb}$ (and thus $D_{hyd,max,i}$ by scaling, see Sec. 2.6) value. Test simulations from $u_{AE} = 1$ down to $u_{AE} = 0.01$, in which Eq. (17) ($D_{hyd,max,cb} = 0$, $\kappa_d = 22$) was replaced within Eq. (14) by

$$\begin{aligned} F_{PDE,i}(L_{AE,i}, \dot{L}_{AE,i}, u_{AE}) &= D_{PDE,i}(F_{AE}(L_{AE,i}, u_{AE})) \cdot \frac{\dot{L}_{AE,i}}{\lambda} \\ &= D_{hyd,max,i} \cdot \frac{F_{AE}(L_{AE,i}, u_{AE})}{F_{max}} \cdot \frac{\dot{L}_{AE,i}}{\lambda} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

($D_{hyd,max,cb} = 2 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ Nsm}^{-1}$, $\kappa_d = 0$), the strain signals were practically indistinguishable at any u_{AE} value. Accordingly, all results from simulations presented in this study are calculated on the basis of feeding Eq. (17) into the force equilibrium Eq. (14).

2.4.2. Drive (AE) and serial elasticity (SE): force-length relations

Two crucial force-length relations constitute the core of our CB model (Fig. 3, bottom-right). They are [37, eq. 40]

$$F_{AE,cb}(L_{AE,cb}) = F_{cb,ref} \cdot \left(\frac{c_{1,cb}}{(L_{AE,cb} + c_{3,cb})^2} + c_{2,cb} \right) \quad , \quad (20)$$

for the AE (the *active drive* within the CB-CE model, i.e. the source of mechanical work), with

$$c_{1,cb} = \frac{c_{3,cb}^2 \cdot (L_{AE,cb,ref} + c_{3,cb})^2}{c_{3,cb}^2 - (L_{AE,cb,ref} + c_{3,cb})^2} \quad (21)$$

$$c_{2,cb} = -\frac{c_{1,cb}}{c_{3,cb}^2} = \frac{(L_{AE,cb,ref} + c_{3,cb})^2}{(L_{AE,cb,ref} + c_{3,cb})^2 - c_{3,cb}^2} \quad (22)$$

$$\text{and length parameter} \quad c_{3,cb} = 1 \text{ nm} \quad \text{chosen here,} \quad (23)$$

as well as [37, eq. 39]

$$F_{SE,cb}(L_{SE,cb}) = K_{SE,cb} \cdot L_{SE,cb} \quad , \quad (24)$$

and

$$F_{SE,hs,fil}(L_{SE,hs,fil}) = K_{SE,hs,fil} \cdot L_{SE,hs,fil} \quad , \quad (25)$$

with

$$L_{SE,hs} = L_{SE,hs,fil} + L_{SE,hs,cb} \quad (26)$$

for the SE (the *passive elasticity* within the CB-CE model), which is made of two contributions that serially transmit any AE force generated by a CB via their combined SE stiffness in a HS: one SE stiffness contribution by a single CB (Eq. (24)), and one lumped from the two filament types, myosin and actin (Eq. (25)); both HS’s SE stiffness contributions are modelled in terms of linearly elastic springs. The (activity-dependent: Eq. (2)) HS’s SE force-length relation follows from $1 \leq n_{hs,cb} \leq n_{hs,cbmax}$ CBs acting in series to one (half-)myosin and two actin filaments (1:2 ratio reflects the lattice’s stoichiometry):

$$F_{SE,hs}(L_{SE,hs}, u_{AE}) = K_{SE,hs}(u_{AE}) \cdot L_{SE,hs} \quad , \quad (27)$$

with

$$K_{SE,hs}(u_{AE}) = \frac{K_{SE,hs,fil} \cdot K_{SE,hs,cb}(u_{AE})}{K_{SE,hs,fil} + K_{SE,hs,cb}(u_{AE})} \cdot L_{SE,hs} \quad , \quad (28)$$

$$K_{SE,hs,cb}(u_{AE}) = u_{AE} \cdot n_{hs,cbmax} \cdot K_{SE,cb} \quad , \quad (29)$$

371 and

$$K_{SE,hs,fil} = \frac{n_{hs,cbmax} \cdot K_{SE,cb} \cdot \frac{F_{cb,ref}}{L_{SE,hs,cbmax}}}{K_{SE,cb} - \frac{F_{cb,ref}}{L_{SE,hs,cbmax}}} \quad (30)$$

372 The latter filament contribution (Eq. (30)) to the HS's SE stiffness is *inferred* from model input parameters due to
 373 fulfilment of the condition

$$K_{SE,hs,max} = n_{hs,cbmax} \cdot \frac{F_{cb,ref}}{L_{SE,hs,cbmax}} = \frac{K_{SE,hs,fil} \cdot K_{SE,hs,cb}(u_{AE} = 1)}{K_{SE,hs,fil} + K_{SE,hs,cb}(u_{AE} = 1)} \quad (31)$$

374 constituted by the rightmost equality in Eq. (31) (i.e. in a maximally activated HS), which is solved for $K_{SE,hs,fil}$.

375 For a variable number of CBs, expressed by activity u_{AE} (Eq. (2)), the force-length relation of one CB in Eq. (20)
 376 simply scales linearly to the force-length relation

$$F_{AE,hs}(L_{AE,cb}) = u_{AE} \cdot n_{hs,cbmax} \cdot F_{AE,cb}(L_{AE,cb}) \quad (32)$$

377 of a HS, due the CBs acting mechanically in parallel in a HS, and likewise does the slope of Eq. (32):

$$K_{AE,hs}(L_{AE,i}, u_{AE}) = -u_{AE} \cdot F_{hs,max} \cdot \frac{2 \cdot c_{1,i}}{(L_{AE,i} + c_{3,i})^3} \quad (33)$$

378 introducing the abbreviation $F_{hs,max} = n_{hs,cbmax} \cdot F_{cb,ref}$.

379 Scaling lengths and forces (hence also stiffnesses and damping coefficients) from a microscopic CB (Eqs. (20-23))
 380 via a HS (Eqs. (32,33)) to a macroscopic CE,i according to Sec. 2.6 yields

$$F_{AE,i}(L_{AE,i}, u_{AE}) = u_{AE} \cdot F_{max,i} \cdot \left(\frac{c_{1,i}}{(L_{AE,i} + c_{3,i})^2} + c_{2,i} \right) \quad (34)$$

381 with the slope

$$K_{AE,i}(L_{AE,i}, u_{AE}) = -u_{AE} \cdot \frac{2 \cdot c_{1,i} \cdot F_{max,i}}{(L_{AE,i} + c_{3,i})^3} \quad (35)$$

382 (length parameters $c_{3,i} = n_{L,hs,i} \cdot c_{3,cb}$ Eq. (23) and $L_{AE,ref,i} = n_{L,hs,i} \cdot L_{AE,cb,ref}$ in $c_{1,cb}$ Eq. (21) scaled according to
 383 Sec. 2.6), as well as (from Eq. (27), and $L_{SE,i} = n_{L,hs,i} \cdot L_{SE,hs}$)

$$F_{SE,i}(L_{SE,i}, u_{AE}) = K_{SE,i}(u_{AE}) \cdot L_{SE,i} \quad (36)$$

384 with the SE stiffness (from Eq. (28))

$$K_{SE,i}(u_{AE}) = \frac{n_{CSA,hs}}{n_{L,hs,i}} \cdot K_{SE,hs}(u_{AE}) \quad (37)$$

385 The integer numbers for scaling, $n_{CSA,hs}$ and $n_{L,hs,i}$, are illustrated in Fig. 5 and explained in Sec. 2.6.

386 Equation (34) implies that the slope of this macroscopic $F_{AE,i}(L_{AE,i}, u_{AE})$ relation scales linearly with activity
 387 u_{AE} , at any working point. The stiffness $K_{SE,i}(u_{AE})$ of an SE,i (Eq. (36)) likewise scales with u_{AE} , even though
 388 non-linearly (Fig. 4). Also, damping strengths on the macroscopic level (see Eqs. (16,17,19)) automatically scale with
 389 activity u_{AE} in our model, as the coefficients are modelled in proportion to $F_{AE,i}$ and $F_{SE,i}$ anyway, and the MTC's
 390 initial (isometric) tension $F_{CE,i} = F_{SE,i} \approx F_{AE,i}$ (\approx due to a PEE potentially being effective) at the instant of
 391 frame impact scales with u_{AE} . Note that initially all CBs in an AE,i act close to their reference position ($L_{AE,cb,ref}$,
 392 $L_{SE,hs,cbmax}$: Fig. 3, bottom-right), even at low activity. This is because, for decreasing macroscopic $F_{CE,i}$ with
 393 $u_{AE} < 1$ and (in our simulations here) holding the MTC at the very isometric length where all CBs settle practically
 394 at their reference position if $u_{AE} = 1$, the TACs' are stiff enough (Table 2) when they increasingly relaxing to leave
 395 the CBs just slightly 'over-stretched', i.e. at lengths longer than for $u_{AE} = 1$, still close to their reference position.

396 *2.5. Connecting the PMs: condensing the basic equations of the CB-CE model into one, the CE,i-internal (con-*
 397 *strained) contraction dynamics*

398 The contraction dynamics of a CE,i subjected to the rheonomic constraint of *given* $\dot{L}_{CE,i}(t)$ is actually a differential
 399 equation of first order that describes the time rate of change $\dot{L}_{SE,i}(t)$ of the SE,i length, i.e. the CE,i-internal DoF.
 400 To derive $\dot{L}_{SE,i}(t)$ as a function of all mechanical properties of the CE,i model formulated above, one solves the

401 kinematic constraint in terms of length rates (Eq. (12)) for $\dot{L}_{AE,i}(t) = \dot{L}_{CE,i}(t) - \dot{L}_{SE,i}(t)$, then substitutes $\dot{L}_{AE,i}(t)$
 402 into the formulation Eq. (14) of the force equilibrium, and finally solves the resulting equation for

$$\dot{L}_{SE,i}(t) = \frac{\lambda \cdot (F_{AE,i}(L_{AE,i}(t), u_{AE}) - F_{SE,i}(L_{SE,i}(t), u_{AE})) + D_{PDE}(F_{SE}(L_{SE,i}(t), u_{AE})) \cdot \dot{L}_{CE,i}(t)}{D_{PDE}(F_{SE,i}(L_{SE,i}(t), u_{AE})) + \lambda \cdot D_{SDE}(F_{SE,i}(L_{SE,i}(t), u_{AE}))}, \quad (38)$$

403 with always keeping in mind the basic kinematic constraint in terms of the lengths themselves: $L_{AE,i}(t) = L_{CE,i}(t) -$
 404 $L_{SE,i}(t)$ (Eq. (11)).

405 Hence, with $L_{CE,i}(t)$ and $L_{SE,i}(t)$ known as system states, and all mechanical element properties given according
 406 to Sec. 2.4, the $i = 1 \dots n_{CE}$ Eqs. (38) being a set of n_{CE} ordinary differential equations of first order can be integrated
 407 in parallel with the frame-and-PMs' system of mechanical equations of motion made of Eqs. (1) and Eq. (6) to predict
 408 the mechanical response of the MTC suspended to the frame being dropped and impacting with the ground (the
 409 frame's 'touch-down', TD) at time $t = \tau_{TD}$.

410 2.6. Scaling from CB via HS to CE,i within the belly part of the muscle-tendon complex (MTC)

411 How the mechanical model parameters scale from the microscopic model level of a HS to the macroscopic one of
 412 CE,i is illustrated in Fig. 5. The scaling rules are plain: (i) A length on HS level is scaled to its equivalent on CE,i
 413 level by multiplying the former with the number $n_{L,hs,i}$ of HSs arranged in series in a CE,i. (ii) A force is scaled from
 414 HS to CE,i level by multiplying the HS parameter with the number $n_{CSA,hs}$ of HS arranged in parallel in the CSA
 415 of a CE,i, i.e. simply and homogeneously also the whole belly part of our model MTC. In particular, AE force on
 416 HS level depends on the (actual) number $n_{hs,cb}$ of CBs in any HS (we assume in our present model that all HSs are
 417 homogeneously activated); accordingly, AE forces on both HS and CE,i levels scale the same, namely, with the global
 418 control parameter *activity* u_{AE} (Eq. (2)). (iii) In accordance with (i) and (ii), and thus their basic physical meaning,
 419 stiffness values, just like those of damping coefficients, scale from HS to CE,i level in linear proportion to $n_{CSA,hs}$
 420 and in inverse proportion to $n_{L,hs,i}$, i.e. with the ratio $\frac{n_{CSA,hs}}{n_{L,hs,i}}$ (e.g. in the case of SE, see Eq. (37)). Consistent
 421 with this, the slope of the AE force-length relation scales like stiffnesses (see Eq. (33), and Eq. (35)); and, owing to
 422 their structural basis in common (CBs in a HS), both the AE force-length slopes and the SE stiffness values scale
 423 in proportion to u_{AE} , whether on HS or CE,i level (see again Eqs. (33,35) and Eqs. (28,37)), linearly in the case of
 424 AEs, non-linearly in the case of SEs (see also Fig. 4). In our default model, we assume that any PEE stiffness does
 425 *not* depend on u_{AE} , somehow implying that such stiffness is due to passive material like endomysium, epimysium,
 426 or perimysium. Nonetheless, in a parameter variation, we have probed how the dynamic strain amplitudes within
 427 the model's belly part (i.e. of all CE,i) change when making PEE stiffnesses u_{AE} -dependent (e.g. thinking of titin
 428 contributions). Table 1 compiles the values of all independent model parameters, and Table 2 crucial stiffness values,
 429 while they also list how these values exactly scale up numerically from CB via HS to CE,i levels.

430 2.7. Initial conditions for dropping the MTC clamped in the frame

431 In all simulations in this study, the model MTC (Fig. 1) designed by the set of independent parameters according
 432 to Table 1 was distally and proximally fixed to the model frame (a rigid body of 12 cm width of the C-shape) at
 433 a fixed length of $L_{CE,opt} + L_{TAC,d,0} + L_{TAC,p,0} + 1.29 \text{ mm} = 46.29 \text{ mm}$. Activity u_{AE} is a control parameter in
 434 our present MTC model; each simulation run was performed with a given, constant activity value. At full activity
 435 $u_{AE} = 1$, all model CBs were therewith very close to their reference lengths (CB positions) $L_{AE,cb,ref}$ at TD, and all
 436 AE,i along the model MTC generated about $F_{AE,i} \approx F_{CE,i} = F_{MTC,TD} = 29.85 \text{ N}$ (with $F_{max} = 30 \text{ N}$). The model
 437 MTC was thus always held close to its optimal length in all simulations in this study. With decreasing u_{AE} and
 438 thus isometric force, the TACs increasingly shortened slightly in accordance their force-length relations fixed, which
 439 induced over-extension of the AE,i. However, the shallow slope of a CB's force-length relation does not change much
 440 with over-extension, and so does neither the stiffness of an AE,i (very low anyway compared to the SE) nor its force.
 441 Therefore, we did not adapt the MTC length (at the order of tens of μm) in our simulations for submaximal activity
 442 values down to $u_{AE} = 0.1$, i.e. when pre-loading the MTC at TD with only about a tenth of its maximum isometric
 443 force F_{max} . The initial (y -)positions of the PMs along the model belly (chain of PMs) were chosen at equal distances
 444 of exactly $L_{CE,opt,i} = \frac{L_{CE,opt}}{n_{CE}} = 1.375 \text{ mm}$, with locating them such that less than 1 N initial force deviations of both
 445 TACs from $F_{MTC,TD}$ occurred at full activity. With these initial conditions, the MTC equilibrated usually within
 446 less than 1 ms after simulation start, except for one simulation case, namely, at $u_{AE} = 0.1$ in our model variation
 447 with u_{AE} -dependent PEE stiffness, in which the MTC still crept at the time of TD. The latter always occurred
 448 shortly after $t = 10 \text{ ms}$, as the frame's initial condition was to be dropped from 2.7 cm height, for providing an impact
 449 velocity of close to 0.73 ms^{-1} , a value approximating the vertical component of a paw's TD velocity in running rats,
 450 and reproducing the experimental situation in [35].

452 The mechanical MTC-frame model sketched in the Figs. 1, 3, 5 was implemented in terms of *C*-code in our in-
453 house multi-body-system program named *simsys* [27, 42, 48, 49, 50, 51], a computer simulation code for reading
454 a parametrised two-dimensional mechanical model description (first of all, the topology of rigid bodies and PMs
455 connected by constraints and interacting by forces and torques) from ASCII-coded input files to transcript this
456 into the equations of motion Eqs. (1) ($n_{CE} + 1$ PMs), Eq. (6) (frame), and Eqs. (38 (n_{CE} CE,i)). *simsys* also offers
457 coding interfaces to feed arbitrary force laws, like those in Sec. 2.4, into Eqs. (1) in terms of user-written *C*-code,
458 and provides functionality to detect the frame's ground contact, in combination with offering pre-parametrised force
459 laws for modelling ground reaction forces, as well as flexible user coding of any desired resulting data output to files.
460 The complete set of the model's equations of motion is eventually formulated within *simsys* as a first-order system
461 of ordinary differential equations. At any time step requested by the time integrating predictor-corrector algorithm
462 *de* (Shampine-Gordon algorithm [52]), this set is solved for the accelerations and velocities by matrix inversion by
463 calling *dgefa* and *dgesl* (from the *LINPACK* package). For the simulations in this study, the three basic numerical
464 parameters for controlling time integration by *de* were the user-requested time step width (0.1 ms), which also fixed
465 the density on the time axis for the output data, as well as user-requested relative (10^{-8}) and absolute (10^{-8})
466 accuracies of the solution (set of state variables). If accuracy demands can be met by *de*, it indicates successful (flag
467 value 2) return of the requested solution after having proceeded one time step.

468

469

unit	cross-bridge		half-sarcomere		one CE (index: i)		all CEs	
1							n_{CE}	24
kg					Figs. 1,2: $\mathcal{M}_i, i = 1 \dots n_{CE} + 1 = 25$		\mathcal{M}	0.002
N					$F_{max,i} = F_{max}$	30.0	F_{max}	30.0
m					$L_{CE,opt,i} = \frac{L_{CE,opt}}{n_{CE}}$	$1.375 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$L_{CE,opt}$	0.033
m			$L_{hs,ref}$	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$				
1					$n_{L,hs,i} = \frac{L_{CE,opt,i}}{L_{hs,ref}}$	1250	$n_{L,hs,all} = \frac{L_{CE,opt}}{L_{hs,ref}}$	$3 \cdot 10^4$
m	$L_{AE,cb,ref}$	$7.0 \cdot 10^{-9}$		$7.0 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$\cdot n_{L,hs,i} = L_{AE,ref,i}$	$8.75 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$\cdot n_{CE} = L_{AE,ref}$	$2.1 \cdot 10^{-4}$
m	$c_{3,cb}$	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-9}$		$1.0 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$\cdot n_{L,hs,i} = c_{3,i}$	$1.25 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$\cdot n_{CE} = c_3$	$3.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$
m			$L_{SE,hs,cbmax}$	$4.0 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$\cdot n_{L,hs,i} = L_{SE,ref,i}$	$5.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$\cdot n_{CE} = L_{SE,ref}$	$1.2 \cdot 10^{-4}$
m			$L_{hs,cbmax} = \frac{L_{AE,cb,ref} + L_{SE,hs,cbmax}}{2}$	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$\cdot n_{L,hs,i} = L_{CE,ref,i}$	$1.375 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$\cdot n_{CE} = L_{CE,ref}$	$3.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$
1			$n_{hs,cbmax}$	100				
N	$F_{cb,ref}$	$4.0 \cdot 10^{-12}$	$\cdot n_{hs,cbmax} = F_{hs,max}$	$4.0 \cdot 10^{-10}$				
1			$u_{AE} = \frac{n_{hs,cb}}{n_{hs,cbmax}}$	0.01 ... 1.0		0.01 ... 1.0		0.01 ... 1.0
1			$n_{hs,cb} = n_{hs,cbmax} \cdot u_{AE}$	1 ...				
1					$n_{CSA,cbmax} = \frac{F_{max}}{F_{cb,ref}}$	$7.5 \cdot 10^{12}$		$7.5 \cdot 10^{12}$
1					$n_{CSA,hs} = \frac{F_{max}}{F_{hs,max}}$	$7.5 \cdot 10^{10}$		$7.5 \cdot 10^{10}$
1					$n_{CSA,cb} = n_{CSA,cbmax} \cdot u_{AE}$	$n_{CSA,hs} \dots$	$n_{CSA,hs} \dots$	$n_{CSA,hs} \dots$
N			$F_{hs,ref} = u_{AE} \cdot F_{hs,max}$	$F_{cb,ref} \dots$	$\cdot n_{CSA,hs} = F_{ref,i}$	0.3 ... 30.0	$F_{ref} = F_{ref,i} = u_{AE} \cdot F_{max}$	0.3 ... 30.0
1	λ	22.0		22.0		22.0		22.0
1	κ_d	λ		λ		λ		λ
Nsm ⁻¹	$D_{def,max,cb}$	$4.0 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$\cdot n_{hs,cbmax} = D_{def,max,hs}$	$4.0 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$\cdot \frac{n_{CSA,hs}}{n_{L,hs,i}} = D_{def,max,i}$	2.4	$\cdot \frac{1}{n_{CE}} = D_{def,max}$	0.1
1	R_{def}	0.01		0.01		0.01		0.01
1					$C_{PEE,i} = C_{PEE}$	0.1	C_{PEE}	0.1
1					$d\mathcal{L}_{PEE,i} = d\mathcal{L}_{PEE}$	0.1	$d\mathcal{L}_{PEE}$	0.1
m							$L_{TAC,d,0}$	0.01
m							$L_{TAC,p,0}$	0.002
1							$\Delta U_{TAC,null}$	0.0425
1							$\Delta U_{TAC,l}$	0.017
1							$\nu_{TAC} = \frac{\Delta U_{TAC,null}}{\Delta U_{TAC,l}}$	2.5
1							f_{TAC}	0.4
N							$\Delta F_{TAC,0} = f_{TAC} \cdot F_{max}$	6.0
s							\mathcal{T}_{TAC}	0.002
Nsm ⁻¹							$D_{TAC,max,d} = \frac{F_{max} \cdot \mathcal{T}_{TAC}}{L_{TAC,d,0}}$	6.0
Nsm ⁻¹							$D_{TAC,max,p} = \frac{F_{max} \cdot \mathcal{T}_{TAC}}{L_{TAC,p,0}}$	30.0
1							R_{TAC}	0.01

Table 1:

Default model: Compilation of all but one (**24** out of **25**; the remaining $K_{SE,cb}$ in Table 2) **independent (bold font)** and some derived model parameter values of the force-generating elements of the fibre material (CE, AE, SE) and the tendon-aponeurosis (TAC) parts, across the four structural levels **taken into account**.

The **framed** macroscopic and microscopic parameters are semantically linked: first of all, F_{max} and $L_{CE,opt}$ reflect the basic macroscopic parameters that can be determined experimentally (thereby defining a unique reference state), namely, the maximum isometric (stationary, at least for about a second [53]) force of the muscle (belly) and the very (belly) length at which this force can be generated; in this *fully activated, full myosin-actin overlap, isometric* condition, the maximally possible number of myosin heads (CBs; $n_{hs,cb} = n_{hs,cbmax}$ on average) is attached in all HSs, i.e. $u_{AE} = \frac{n_{hs,cb}}{n_{hs,cbmax}} = 1$ in our model; the latter microscopic condition is referred to by using the index ‘ ref ’ primarily for the corresponding HS length

$L_{hs,ref}$, but also—this, though, being another simplifying, averaging assumption in our present model—the length condition of *any* CB (defining its internal DoF, see green transverse line in the CB model, Fig. 3, top-right and bottom-left) and HS in this isometric reference state (the macroscopic correspondence: optimal, $L_{CE,opt}$) characterised by the length parameters $L_{AE,cb,ref}$ and $L_{SE,hs,cbmax}$ in combination with the corresponding CB ($F_{cb,ref}$) and HS ($F_{hs,max}$) forces.

The muscle mass \mathcal{M} is **0.002** kg, see rightmost part of Fig. 1 for its separation into $n_{CE} + 1 = 25$ PMs with each a mass \mathcal{M}_i (mass distribution in Fig. 2).

By setting $\kappa_d = 0$ and $D_{hyd,max,cb} = \kappa_d \cdot \lambda \cdot D_{def,max,cb} \approx 2 \cdot 10^{-7}$ Nsm⁻¹, we tested exchanging $F_{SE,i}$ -dependency of $D_{PDE,i}$ (thus $F_{PDE,i}$, Eq. (17)) by $F_{AE,i}$ -dependency (Eq. (19)).

cross-bridge		half-sarcomere		one CE (index: i)		all CEs	
$K_{SE,cb}$	$3.0 \cdot 10^{-3}$						
		$K_{SE,hs,fil}$ (Eq. (30))	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-1}$				
		$K_{SE,hs,max}$ (Eq. (31))	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$\cdot \frac{n_{CSA,hs}}{n_{L,hs,i}} = K_{SE,max,i}$	$6.0 \cdot 10^6$	$\cdot \frac{1}{n_{CE}} = K_{SE,max}$	$2.5 \cdot 10^5$
		$K_{SE,hs}(u_{AE} = 0.1)$ (Eqs. (28,29,30))	$2.5 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$\cdot \frac{n_{CSA,hs}}{n_{L,hs,i}} = K_{SE,med,i}$	$1.5 \cdot 10^6$	$\cdot \frac{1}{n_{CE}} = K_{SE,med}$	$6.25 \cdot 10^4$
		$K_{SE,hs}(u_{AE} = 0.01)$ (Eqs. (28,29,30))	$2.94 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$\cdot \frac{n_{CSA,hs}}{n_{L,hs,i}} = K_{SE,min,i}$	$1.76 \cdot 10^5$	$\cdot \frac{1}{n_{CE}} = K_{SE,min}$	7,350
$K_{AE,cb,0}$	$8.1 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$\cdot n_{hs,cbmax} = K_{AE,hs,0,max}$	$8.1 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$\cdot \frac{n_{CSA,hs}}{n_{L,hs,i}} = K_{AE,0,max,i}$	$4.88 \cdot 10^7$	$\cdot \frac{1}{n_{CE}} = K_{AE,0,max}$	$2.03 \cdot 10^6$
$K_{AE,cb,ref}$	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$\cdot n_{hs,cbmax} = K_{AE,hs,ref,max}$	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$\cdot \frac{n_{CSA,hs}}{n_{L,hs,i}} = K_{AE,ref,max,i}$	$9.52 \cdot 10^4$	$\cdot \frac{1}{n_{CE}} = K_{AE,ref,max}$	3970.0
		$K_{AE,hs,ref,min}$ (i.e. $u_{AE} = 0.01$)	$K_{AE,cb,ref}$	$\cdot \frac{n_{CSA,hs}}{n_{L,hs,i}} = K_{AE,ref,min,i}$	952.0	$\cdot \frac{1}{n_{CE}} = K_{AE,ref,min}$	39.7
		$K_{PEE,hs} = C_{PEE} \cdot K_{AE,hs,ref,max}$	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$\cdot \frac{n_{CSA,hs}}{n_{L,hs,i}} = K_{PEE,i}$	9520.0	$\cdot \frac{1}{n_{CE}} = K_{PEE}$	397.0
						$K_{TAC,d}$	$3.53 \cdot 10^4$
						$K_{TAC,p}$	$1.76 \cdot 10^5$

Table 2:

Default model: Stiffness values (unit: Nm^{-1} ; ' $_{max}$ ' indicates: at maximum activity $u_{AE} = 1$); except for $K_{SE,cb}$, all derived from the independent parameters compiled in Table 1, of the fibre material (CE, AE, SE) and tendon-aponeurosis (TAC) parts, across the four structural levels taken into account.

On each model level above a single cross-bridge, the actual AE stiffness value is activity ($0.01 \leq u_{AE} \leq 1$) times the ' $_{max}$ '-indicated value given here (minimum case with $u_{AE} = 0.01$ indicated by ' $_{min}$ '); SE stiffnesses from the HS through more macroscopic levels are likewise u_{AE} -dependent (see Eqs. (28,29,30)) and the ratio of SE and AE stiffnesses in Fig. 4); PEE stiffnesses are assumed to be u_{AE} -independent, CE values arise from the serial arrangement of SE and AE (plus PEE).

$$K_{AE,cb,ref} = 2 \cdot \frac{F_{cb,ref}}{L_{AE,cb,ref}} \cdot \frac{c_{3,cb}^2}{(L_{AE,cb,ref} + c_{3,cb}) \cdot (L_{AE,cb,ref} + 2 \cdot c_{3,cb})}, \quad K_{AE,cb,0} = 2 \cdot \frac{F_{cb,ref}}{L_{AE,cb,ref}} \cdot \frac{(L_{AE,cb,ref} + c_{3,cb})^2}{c_{3,cb} \cdot (L_{AE,cb,ref} + 2 \cdot c_{3,cb})}$$

According to the short-range stiffness distribution within the MTC, determined during physiological impact responses as compiled in this table, the overall MTC stiffness in these conditions (which include absence of significant detachment-reattachment dynamics during the initial oscillatory response of the rat GAS MTC, i.e. frame contact time $\tau_{con} \approx 12$ ms) is practically determined by the AE stiffness. For submaximal activity, $u_{AE} < 1$, actual AE stiffness values scale down in linear proportion with u_{AE} from the one indicated by ' $_{max}$ ' on all levels from HS through more macroscopic ones (see Eqs. (34,36)). The same applies to the force-dependent damping coefficients of PDE and SDE (see Eqs. (16,17)).

3. Results

A major part of the results presented is the strain

$$\delta_j(t) = \frac{L_j(t) - L_j(t = \tau_{TD})}{L_{j,ref}} = \frac{\Delta L_j(t)}{L_{j,ref}} \quad (39)$$

in a region of the belly, whether from the modelled CE part of the MTC (distances between two selected PMs) or from rat muscle experiments (distances between two selected clouds, ranges, of surface markers). In Eq. (39), L_j can mean any specific, usually time-dependent length, $L_{j,TD} = L_j(t = \tau_{TD})$ is the associated length at TD, and $L_{j,ref}$ is to be specified in each particular case, being either a reference length from anatomy or $L_{j,TD}$.

The key result of our simulation study is, in fact, implicit literature knowledge, which has to the best of our knowledge not been exposed so far: In an MTC's dynamic strain response to an impact, the deformations within the SE of a muscle fibre are minuscule (see Fig. 6, left) as compared with those in the AE (the muscle's drive, its source of work). In other words: It is *not* the well-known elasticity of the sarcomeres, including passively deformable material of the CBs, that complies, but the compliance is located in the heart of a CB's active drive, probably the space between repelling electric charges. This is because the stiffness of the SE is simply much too high to explain experimentally observable belly strains. It can be inferred that an AE must exist, which has been implemented in our model. Concretely, in a fully activated belly ($u_{AE} = 1$), the stiffness of a HS's SE ($K_{SE,hs,max}$) is more than fifty (exactly 63) times higher than that of the AE ($K_{AE,hs,ref,max}$) around the (reference) working point at $F_{cb,ref}$ of its CBs, see Table 2, and Fig. 4 showing actually the (inverse) ratio $\frac{K_{AE,hs}}{K_{SE,hs}}$ as a function of u_{AE} . At the reference point with $u_{AE} = 0.1$, the ratio $\frac{K_{SE,hs}}{K_{AE,hs}}$ is even 158, see again Fig. 4. Therefore, also an upper bound of the damping force F_{SDE} in parallel to the SE is so low (see Fig. 6, bottom, right) that it is not functional, simply irrelevant in comparison with F_{SE} , F_{AE} , and F_{PDE} , in impact responses at physiological intensity levels like those present in our rat muscle impact experiments, which is reproduced by our wobbling mass model in this study.

3.1. Damping in simulating impact responses

The strength $D_{def,max,cb}$ of a CB's SDE coefficient $d_{def,cb}(F_{SE,cb})$ (Eq. (15)) is still implemented in our CB model via $D_{SDE,i}(F_{SE,i})$ (Eq. (16), from scaled Eq. (15), substituted into Eq. (14)), and assumed to be effective in the PDE via $D_{PDE,i}$ (Eq. (17) into Eq. (14)), based on the idea of some kind of 'joint friction' within the CB [37, p. 160]. A first guess $D_{def,max,cb} \approx 1.0 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ Nsm}^{-1}$ could be estimated from our former experimental analyses of MTC impact responses (see [36, fig. 2d]). There, a damping strength of $d_{hs,max} \approx 2 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ Nsm}^{-1}$ had actually been determined experimentally as an overall value of *one HS* at full activity (see [36, fig. 2d]). This experimental value can then be attributed (via present-model-based scaling) by division by $\kappa_d \cdot n_{hs,cb,max}$ (with $\kappa_d = 22$ [37, equ. 33], $n_{hs,cb,max} = 100$) to the contribution of *one CB* in the d_{def} part of D_{PDE} (compare again [37, equ. 33] within our model Eqs. (14-17)). That is, this estimation results from a thought experiment, in which the *entire* damping effect within one HS is attributed to D_{PDE} . Thus, it *adopts*, first of all, the distribution of local dynamic strains gained from our present model simulations, which in turn are based on an experimentally well-established distribution of local stiffness values, and, second, *conceives of solely* the d_{def} mechanism within D_{PDE} as being the cause of *all* HS damping. It turned out that our simulations here well confirmed the experimentally determined value $d_{hs,max} \approx 2 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ Nsm}^{-1}$. In fact, a 60% reduction to a corresponding model value of $D_{def,max,cb} = 4 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ Nsm}^{-1}$ was generally a good choice to reproduce measured peak values of strain averaged across a more proximal region of the muscle belly (compare right column of Fig. 9 with [35, fig. 5]) while avoiding over-damping. The latter was checked by halving to $D_{def,max,cb} = 2 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ Nsm}^{-1}$, which still yielded realistic peak strain values, however, came along with moderate terminal over-shoot already occurring at higher activity $u_{AE} = 0.25$.

Now *hypothetically* interpreting $d_{hs,max} \approx 2 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ Nsm}^{-1}$ from [36, fig. 2d] as a reflection of the $d_{hyd}(F_{AE})$ instead of the $d_{def}(F_{SE})$ part [37, equ. 33] of $D_{PDE,i}$ (i.e. implementing Eq. (19) instead of Eq. (17) in our model) would give, by multiplying $d_{hs,max}$ by $\frac{\lambda}{n_{hs,cb,max}}$, a guess $D_{hyd,max,cb} \approx 5 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ Nsm}^{-1}$ for a CB's $D_{PDE,cb}$. Note that the λ enumerator here is due to $d_{hs,max}$ in [36, fig. 2d] being defined as the multiplier to \dot{L}_{AE} for calculating the PDE force generated by the HS, whereas D_{PDE} is defined in [37, equ. 12]) (i.e. Eq. (14)) as the multiplier to $\frac{\dot{L}_{AE}}{\lambda}$ for modelling a single CB's PDE contribution to HS force. Corresponding to our final choice $D_{def,max,cb} = 4 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ Nsm}^{-1}$, a value $D_{hyd,max,cb} = 2 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ Nsm}^{-1}$ was used in our simulations with $\kappa = 0$, which proved the practical numerical equivalence (in impact responses) of both alternative D_{PDE} implementations, i.e. modelling $F_{PDE,i}$ by either Eq. (17) (our model default) or Eq. (19).

518 Before presenting the main results of our MTC impact simulations, we show a new finding obtained from re-
 519 analysing the experimental data basis of [35], which provides additional material for model validation.

520 3.2. Experimentally determined strain of an MTC's fibre material in response to an impact of its suspension

521 3.2.1. Methodical details of experimental data analysis

522 We used the same animal experimental setup as earlier [36, 35] to probe the *M25PM* model predictions regarding
 523 local muscle fibre length changes. In brief, that setup consisted of a rat's GAS clamped in a right-angled, C-shaped
 524 frame, which we let drop on the ground, with two high-speed cameras (frame rate: 1825 Hz) capturing the muscle
 525 displacement that followed (wobbling muscle mass). The basic design of this experimental setup is reflected by the
 526 sketch in Fig. 1 of our simulation model. Going an analysis step beyond [36, 35], instead of segmenting only one fibre
 527 material region (*CE*, contractile element) from the muscle-tendon complex (MTC) there, we here subdivided the
 528 *CE* into two regions: a proximal (*CE,p*) and a distal (*CE,d*) one (see Fig. 7d). From marker kinematics smoothed
 529 with a 3-point moving average filter, we segmented the regions *CE,p*, *CE,d*, and *CE* from the rest of GAS with the
 530 vertical distance between two horizontally segmented ranges (marker clouds) located on fibre material; the vertical
 531 position of each range was the arithmetic mean of all markers it contained (see Fig. 7d). The mean values of the
 532 three vertical range positions y_p , y_c , and y_d along the GAS MTC at TD are given in Table 3, as are in its caption the
 533 three distances of these ranges at TD, the (initial) lengths $L_{CE,p,TD} = L_{CE,p}(t = \tau_{TD})$, $L_{CE,d,TD} = L_{CE,d}(t = \tau_{TD})$,
 534 and $L_{CE,TD} = L_{CE}(t = \tau_{TD})$ of the regions *CE,p*, *CE,d*, and *CE*, respectively. In each trial, time $t = \tau_{TD}$ of TD was
 535 determined as the very sample that preceded the instant at which the acceleration of GAS' CoM (a_{CoM}) had risen
 536 above the noise level for the first time. The CoM's vertical position y_{CoM} was estimated by the arithmetic mean of
 537 all 0.4 mm steel markers spread across the belly (50 to 60). The course of the dynamic force fluctuation accelerating
 538 the CoM of the MTC by $a_{CoM}(t)$ in the vertical direction in response to the impact at TD was calculated as

$$\Delta F(t - \tau_{TD}) = \mathcal{M}_{GAS} \cdot (a_{CoM}(t - \tau_{TD}) + g) \quad , \quad (40)$$

539 with $\mathcal{M}_{GAS} = \mathcal{M} = 2 \text{ g}$ being the mass of GAS.

540 3.2.2. Main findings of the experimental analysis

541 Re-analysing the data set from [35], the peak value ΔF_{peak} (maximum) of $\Delta F(t - \tau_{TD})$ averaged across the
 542 exemplary trials was $\overline{\Delta F}_{peak} = 0.34 \text{ N}$. However, it can be seen in [35, fig. 7] that the re-analysed trials seem to
 543 be separable into two clusters, one with $\overline{\Delta F}_{peak} \approx 0.22 \dots 0.3 \text{ N}$, and one with $\overline{\Delta F}_{peak} \approx 0.35 \dots 0.43 \text{ N}$, for which
 544 at least two explanations may be suggested: Either the friction between the frame's protruding grips and the rail
 545 varied over the days of the experiments (e.g. a varying degree of some cant) or muscle bellies differed significantly
 546 in strengths or rest lengths of their (potentially activity-dependent) parallel elasticities. While knowing the length
 547 courses $L_{CE,p}(t)$, $L_{CE,d}(t)$, and $L_{CE}(t)$ (i.e. the $L_j(t)$), we calculated the corresponding local fibre strain courses $\delta_j(t)$
 548 via Eq. (39) by equating the TD length with the reference length $L_{j,ref}$. The values of maximum strain $\delta_{j,max}$ observed
 549 in the exemplary trials are given in Table 4, together with time spans after TD at which the maxima occurred. No
 550 matter the scatter in the oscillatory strain amplitudes for a range of isometric MTC TD forces ('activities': Fig. 7),
 551 the main finding is that the strain was always positive (intermediate lengthening) in the proximal and negative
 552 (intermediate shortening) in the distal belly parts, and very low in the belly's centre. Notably, the oscillatory strain
 553 patterns in the muscle experiments (Fig. 7) may well be explained by a speciality of our experimental setup: As
 554 soon as the frame had deformed the cushion on the ground to a certain degree, a hook fixed to the frame's bottom
 555 cantilever was pushed by a buffer stop to pivot underneath a pin fixed to the ground, i.e. the frame was stopped
 556 from rebounding by a locking latch mechanism [35, fig. 1]. Here, we abstained from modelling this mechanism, as it
 557 is a non-requirement for validating our model based on the initial strain peak after TD; that is, we kept the model
 558 as simple as possible. Accordingly the model frame rebounded and always lifted off again about 12 ms (its contact
 559 time τ_{con}) after TD, not offering the model MTC a space-fixed suspension for regions of its belly mass distribution
 560 to potentially further oscillate around.

symbol	y_p	y_c	y_d	$L_{belly,0}$	$L_{CE,p}$	$L_{CE,d}$	L_{CE}	$L_{TAC,d}$	$L_{MTC,0}^\dagger$
position or length at TD [mm]	38.3	27.8	17.8	33.8	10.5	10.0	20.5	10.6	46.4
% of $L_{belly,0}$, from distal	82.0	50.9	21.3						

Table 3:

Mean positions y_p , y_c , and y_d of marker cloud ranges (Fig. 7d) along the GAS belly of length $L_{belly,0}$ (Table 3).

Positions of y_p , y_c , and y_d were measured relative to $y = 0$, i.e. the origin of the distal GAS (Achilles) tendon (insertion into the calcaneus); accordingly, the origin of the proximal GAS tendon (insertion into the femur) is at $y = L_{MTC,0} = 46.4$ mm. All estimates in this table are mean values, across analysed trials, of the ranges and regions shown in Fig. 7a-c.

† Here, $L_{MTC,0}$ is the mean length of the MTC, calculated in accordance with [35], i.e. $L_{TAC,p} = 2$ mm is implied.

	u_{AE}	$\delta_{j,max}$ [%]	time [ms]	source
CE_p	0.30	1.19	8.8	Fig. 7a
CE_d	0.30	-0.87	8.2	Fig. 7b
CE	0.30	0.30	7.1	Fig. 7c
CE_p	0.48	1.09	8.2	Fig. 7a
CE_d	0.48	-0.39	8.8	Fig. 7b
CE	0.48	0.49	8.2	Fig. 7c
CE_p	0.66	0.49	6.0	Fig. 7a
CE_d	0.66	-0.43	5.6	Fig. 7b
CE	0.66	0.32	9.8	Fig. 7c
CE_p	0.72	0.61	6.0	Fig. 7a
CE_d	0.72	-0.3	6.0	Fig. 7b
CE	0.72	0.36	5.5	Fig. 7c
CE_p	0.80	0.33	6.0	Fig. 7a
CE_d	0.80	-0.09	4.9	Fig. 7b
CE	0.80	0.06	6.6	Fig. 7c
\overline{CE}_p	0.59	0.74	7.3	
\overline{CE}_d	0.59	-0.47	6.9	
\overline{CE}	0.59	0.31	7.4	

Table 4:

Maximum local strain $\delta_{j,max}$ values in GAS muscle fibres as a response to an impact, the time spans from TD to this event, and the estimated fibre activity u_{AE} .

In the $\delta_{j,max}$ calculations (Eq. (39)), whole belly length $L_{belly,0} = 33.8$ mm (Table 3) served as reference length $L_{j,ref}$; time from TD to when $\delta_{j,max}$ occurs is calculated by multiplying the inverse of high-speed cameras' recording frequency (1825 Hz^{-1}) with the number of samples from TD until the $\delta_{j,max}$ event; to specify activity u_{AE} , a uniform value $F_{GAS,max} = 30$ N of the maximum isometric force was assumed [35].

u_{AE}	0.1	0.25	0.5	0.75	1.0
peak strain [%]	0.67	0.58	0.44	0.25	0.05

Table 5:

Simulated (default model, Table 1) peak strain values in response to the suspending frame impacting the ground versus activity u_{AE} .

Analysed signals have been averaged across 14 CE,i ranging from the second-most proximal one to the third distally from the centre of the modelled belly, in accordance with the corresponding range in rat GAS experiments (compare to [35, fig. 5]).

3.3. Reduced models ($M2PM$, $M3PM$, and $M4PM$)

Before looking at the simulation results for the model $M25PM$, which all right seems to well approximate the real belly's mass distribution along its length, we very shortly collect the main observations on the strain responses of the three simplest models, which represent MTC mass by two ($M2PM$), three ($M3PM$), or four ($M4PM$) PMs.

The amplitude of the strain signal of the only CE in $M2PM$ (Fig. 8, left) is two orders of magnitude lower than those observable in $M3PM$ (Fig. 8, middle). In the latter model, there are two CEs, a distal and a proximal one; the distal CE goes through one shortening excursion during frame contact with the ground, while the proximal CE conversely through only lengthening, both courses of nearly the same amplitude. This pattern is already what is generally found for the complex 25-PM model $M25PM$ (Fig. 9, middle). Yet, $M4PM$ with three CEs is the lowest model complexity level, in which all main features of the general pattern of an MTC impact response emerges (compare Fig. 8, right with Fig. 7 and CE_d versus CE_p in Table 4): consistent shortening in the distal region, consistent lengthening in the proximal region, and, compared with the amplitudes in these two, a nearly vanishing amplitude in the centre, very close to what is observable in $M2PM$. Moreover, the distal and proximal strain amplitudes of $M4PM$ come already close to the average strain signals in the corresponding regions of complex $M25PM$. Accordingly, $M4PM$ should be the simplest promising model proxy for further analysing general features of muscle impact responses like, for example, functionally relevant eigenfrequencies of the MTC.

3.4. The complex model ($M25PM$)

The most essential result of our simulation study has already been addressed in the introductory part of this 'Results' section: The strain in the muscle fibre material as a response to an MTC exposed to impacts on physiological intensity level occurs, in fact, solely at the heart of the CB's active drive, rather than in the filaments' and cross-bridges' elastic material (Fig. 6, left). Some other observations in our impact simulations are noteworthy.

3.4.1. Global MTC dynamics

The contact time τ_{con} of the frame is practically independent of the MTC properties, because the latter is stiff (determined by K_{AE} , with some addition of K_{PEE} , maximum: $K_{AE,ref,max}$ Table 2) and its mass is only $\mathcal{M} = 2\text{g}$, which yields the lowest MTC eigenfrequency of about 225 Hz (with $u_{AE} = 1$: $\approx K_{AE,ref,max}$), and 71 Hz (with $u_{AE} = 0.1$: $\approx \frac{K_{AE,ref,max}}{10}$), respectively. In contrast, the frame mass is $\mathcal{M}_{fra} = 52\text{g}$, and its eigenfrequency due to interaction with cushion stiffness K_{cush} is therefore about 44 Hz (see right after Eq. (7)), which well predicts the $\tau_{con} \approx 12\text{ms}$, as the half-period corresponding to the frame-cushion eigenfrequency is 11.3 ms.

According to this givenness of eigenfrequencies, both the contact times and the force fluctuations (in relation to the isometric pre-load) are practically constant across activities and other parameter variations dealt with in this study, which match the experimentally found values well. This is even though the frame is stopped from lifting off in the experiments, whereas the model frame rebounds freely after τ_{con} : The initial oscillatory CE strain response occurs as well in the model as in the experiments [35, fig. 4] within nearly the above predicted basic eigenfrequency's half-period, which is eventually not surprising due to the *half*-period being crucial until the stopping condition in the experiment interferes. Regarding the amplitude ΔF_{peak} of the force fluctuation that re-directs the momentum of the MTC, however, some further comment is expedient. Particularly, the experimental analysis calculated the force fluctuations from solely marker kinematics. Therein, it was implicitly *assumed* that each marker represented the *same* mass portion. Yet, markers have definitely not been evenly distributed on the surface of the muscle belly. In the experiments, they were somehow randomly located, as strict control of the scattering of their mutual distances was impossible, even though the experimenter had absolutely sought to spread them all over the belly. Consequently, the assumption was for sure not fulfilled. However, our simulation can now quantify how much assuming *homogeneous* mass distribution in our experimental analysis work flow distorts the inferred peak value of the force fluctuation ΔF_{peak} . In the example Fig. 6, top, right), with $u_{AE} = 0.75$, this is about 0.455 N in the simulation with *inhomogeneous* distribution, however, assuming in an analysis of this computer experiment that the distribution was *homogeneous*, we find 0.395 N, which is an under-estimation by about 0.06 N, or 13%. This result matches the experimental data cluster $\overline{\Delta F}_{peak} \approx 0.35 \dots 0.43\text{N}$ in [35, fig. 7] very well.

3.4.2. Local fibre strains in the default parameter case

The local strain patterns of $M25PM$ as a response to frame impact (Fig. 9, middle, e.g., look at the top, with $u_{AE} = 0.1$) are stereotyped: The local amplitudes increase from the practically non-strained belly centre to always shortening distally, and lengthening proximally, with the amplitudes being proximally roughly 20% higher than at the mirrored position in the distal direction. Accordingly, the maximum amplitudes occur at the proximal and distal

ends of the 'belly', i.e. in both outermost CE,*i* terminating the chain of PMs, of which each pulls on its respective PM. These maximum peaks are about 2.5 times higher than what is observable in *M4PM*. For immediate comparison with experimental CE strain data as a function of isometric force at TD, plotted in [35, fig. 5], we have performed *M25PM* simulations for five activity values u_{AE} (0.1, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, and 1.0). The course of the simulated CE,*i* strain signals' arithmetic mean value, at each time sample from the distally second outermost CE,*i* ('#23', CE,23) to the third one beyond the centre ('#10', CE,10), is plotted versus time in Fig. 9, right. This region for averaging across CE,10-CE,23 approximates the one in the rat GAS experiments, as depicted in [35, fig. 1B]. The simulated peak values of these averaged strain signals in dependence of u_{AE} (Table 5) fall well into the measured data range [35, fig. 5]. The strain peaks gained from our re-analysis that strove to separate the distal from the proximal regions (Table 4) are about double as high as in [35, fig. 1B] and Table 5, which makes all three analyses consistent, because the region of averaging in the latter two data sets firstly excludes the proximally outermost part of the belly, in which the highest lengthening amplitude occurs, and secondly includes some shortening parts slightly distal to the centre. Values of lengthening strain maxima near the proximal end of the belly reaching almost 2% (Fig. 9, middle, top: $u_{AE} = 0.1$) are addressed in the discussion, as this would mean a CB's (over-)stretch of almost twice its work stroke length.

3.4.3. Some parameter variations

Beyond using our default parameter set, we have run impact simulations with the MTC model varied in four ways. We particularly probed the sensitivity of the model belly's strain signals with regard to force-length properties (Fig. 3, bottom, right and PEE stiffness, Fig. 5, rightmost), be them active or passive (elastic), and the inhomogeneity of the assumed mass distribution (Fig. 2). In the resulting data of these variations, we looked again at our simulated strain signals averaged across the very region (according to [35, fig. 1B]) that approximates the one in the rat GAS experiments, i.e. the CE region CE,10-CE,23.

Assuming the PEE stiffness to go in linear proportion to activity u_{AE} increases peak strain non-linearly with decreasing u_{AE} (from bottom to top in Fig. 10, middle), for $u_{AE} = 0.1$, the peak value is almost tripled (about 1.8%) as compared to the default case of constant PEE stiffness (Fig. 10, left). In case the PEE is completely left away (Fig. 10, right) and at lower activities $u_{AE} \leq 0.5$, the CE still creep at the instant of TD, i.e. have not attained exact isometric equilibrium. This is as we started any simulation in the same MTC length condition, which we chose to be very close to where the AE,*i* of the model CBs act at their reference length $L_{AE,cb,ref}$ and force $F_{cb,ref}$ (representing 'start of work stroke') at full activity; hence, the AE,*i* first had to settle (during the free fall of the frame) at some degree of over-stretch (see Fig. 6, top, left) at lower activities. Evidently, a relatively low PEE stiffness of a tenth of the AE force-length slope at the reference condition (Table 1: $d\mathcal{L}_{PEE,i} = 0.1$) is enough to highly accelerate such settling to an isometric (steady-state) condition of the CBs.

Not surprisingly, our CB-mechanics-based model is very sensitive to varying the slope of the CB's AE force-length relation (Eq. (20)), which is determined by its sole independent input parameter $c_{3,cb}$. Increasing its default value of 1 nm by 50% induces an increased $F_{AE,cb}(L_{AE,cb})$ slope, thus, less compliance of the CB's AE, and accordingly generally reduced strain amplitudes (compare Fig. 11, middle with left). The amplitude reduction is even a little stronger than by a factor of 1.5, therefore the term "very sensitive".

Finally, we replaced the inhomogeneous mass distribution, which is to approximate the tapered form of the real muscle belly, by the simplest case, namely, assigning the same mass $\frac{M}{n_{CE}+1} = 0.08$ g to each PM, termed 'homogeneous mass distribution' (compare both cases in Fig. 2). The homogeneous mass distribution measurably reduces the strain amplitudes (compare Fig. 11, right with left), however, this feature is less important than the force-length properties probed above. The reduction is an effect of significantly increasing the mass portions at the belly ends, which increases the inert resistance of them being displaced relative to their PM neighbour(s in the chain) by a dynamic force gradient (induced by the stiffness gradient) between the adjacent TAC and CE,*i*, respectively.

4. Discussion

In this study, we have given good theoretical evidence that the mechanical response of an MTC to an impact with physiologically customary intensity is determined by the interaction of four crucial properties: (a) the slope of the force-length relation of the very structure that constitutes the source of work (drive, motor, engine) within the CBs, i.e. the compliance at the heart of the muscle, (b) the strength of the frictional damping that additionally resists the deformation of this structure, (c) the MTC's own mass distribution (in particular within the belly), and (d) the stiffnesses of the distal and proximal TACs. Moreover, it seems settled that elastic structures in parallel to

663 the basic four-element structure of a CB, which is transferred to model a HS, are non-negligible, be them of passive
664 (e.g. endo-, epi-, or perimysium) or very likely even active (titin-actin interaction [54, 55, 56]) character.

665 Only with implementing and combining these four *structure-based* muscle properties in an MTC model, suspending
666 the MTC model in a model frame, dropping it on the ground, and parametrically ‘activating’ the MTC’s belly part,
667 i.e. with letting all crucial mechanical properties and side conditions of the corresponding muscle experiments
668 dynamically interact at once, it became possible to, somewhat surprisingly, find that the compliance in the muscle
669 fibres in response to inescapable, customary impacts is *exactly not due to* the fibre-inherent, well-known passive
670 stiffness of the filaments and the CB molecules (like the light chain domain), i.e. the structure termed SE, *but due to*
671 compliance at the heart of the CB drive (probably a gap bridged by an electro-static field), i.e. the structure termed
672 AE.

673 A pretty far-reaching inference can be suggested therefrom, as the AE’s force-length relation in our model has
674 been technically derived [47, eq. 20, fig. 2],[37, eq. 40, fig. 4] from rapid step experiments [38, 39, 40, 57, 58, 59, 60]. On
675 the one hand, it is *assumed* that the AE’s force-length relation can be traced back to basic *electro-static charge-charge*
676 *repulsion (Coulomb interaction)* [46]—or maybe *dipole-dipole repulsion* [45]—and, on the other hand, the estimated
677 Coulomb force’s charge-charge distance (about 3 nm [37, fig. 4]) is *predicted* by a corresponding model [37] to change
678 by about 0.3 nm [37, fig. 4]) through a whole work stroke. The latter, *in turn, is close to* the very 0.5 nm shift
679 within the CB’s active site that has been *observed* [61, pp. 702-703] on the basis of visualisations of conformational
680 changes of the myosin head in a work stroke. Hence, we suggest that the key mechanism that explains the muscle’s
681 impact response is a plain and classical force interaction between its local mass inertia and the work-generating
682 driving forces generated (by Coulomb or electric dipole repulsion) in the active sites of the CBs. Consistently, the
683 measurable damping is likewise suggested to occur due to probably classical friction that resists any shift (change in
684 charge-charge distance) in the active site going hand in hand with the tilt of a myosin head. Accordingly, it can be
685 inferred from the observed global force fluctuations (in the TACs, or the belly’s CoM, respectively) and local strains
686 of up to about one work stroke length (11 nm, 1% strain; short range ‘stiffness’ [63]) that the mechanics of impact
687 responses are dominated by the properties of non-disrupted CBs. Any longer range displacement mechanisms (see
688 very recently [56]: “small” in-between “short range” and “long range”) come with forcible CB disruption, and maybe
689 best described (and modelled) by ‘protein friction’ [64, 65, 66, 67, 68, 69, 70].

690 That said, we call attention to the observation in our simulations that the amplitudes of the model-predicted,
691 pretty stereotyped, distal-to-proximal strain patterns within the belly are excessive towards both belly ends (slightly
692 above 2% at low activities, even in the presence of moderate PEE ‘assistance’). This appears to be definitely
693 inconsistent with the idea of non-disrupted CBs. Unfortunately, the spatial resolution of our experiments [36, 35]
694 was insufficient to analyse strains localised enough right close to the fibre-aponeuroses junctions. Future experiments
695 will clarify. For the time being, at least two alternatives can be offered as hypotheses on what may actually happen
696 near these junctions in in-situ muscles: (i) The design of fibres terminating usually in an at least slightly pennate
697 orientation at the deformable aponeurosis (off the tendon direction) provides a decoupling of the strain in the
698 assembly of the terminating fibres, which interact with the deforming aponeurosis, from their strain component
699 along the tendon direction. Our present MTC model cannot capture this fibre-aponeurosis interaction, apart from
700 the question of whether this would even require the third dimension to take effect, because the present (effectively
701 one-dimensional) model constrains any local fibre strain to occur solely along the direction of the tendons, rather
702 than allow a potential displacement component of a fibre part (and also its mass) perpendicular to its direction,
703 induced by aponeurosis strain. (ii) A second hypothesis would be that CBs are indeed forcibly disrupted on a regular
704 basis near the fibres’ aponeurosis-tendon junctions, which would certainly increase energy dissipation (due to ‘protein
705 friction’), and be considered a design tribute to other functional benefits gained from implementing tendons in the
706 motor apparatus, e.g. enhancing maximum running speed [23].

707 Activated fibres of skeletal vertebrate muscle, like the rat’s GAS in the experiments [36, 35] simulated in the present
708 study, have also been exposed to a highly dynamic boundary condition other than a customary impact, namely, frog
709 *m. tibialis anterior* fibres to sinusoidal strain oscillations of 0.2 % amplitude at 4000 Hz [41]. These conditions are, on
710 the one hand, far away from physiologically customary loading situations, yet, on the other hand, they are perfectly
711 suitable to specifically target at determining the HS’s (short range) stiffness (in our present model terminology: SE
712 and AE combined) at varying levels of fibre activity. What follows shows that “SE and AE combined” can well be
713 a fallacious idea. Since, as we have found that the model’s HS compliance due to the AE’s force-length slope is,
714 in the most common CB conditions, between one and two orders of magnitude higher than that of the SE (which
715 well represents measured passive elastic properties of filaments and myosin heads combined), our model appears, at
716 first glance, to be dismissed right away by exactly the results of this study [41]. This is because they unambiguously

determined SE stiffness values as implemented in our model (filaments and myosin heads). *However*, if it is taken into account, as with both the SDE and PDE in our present model, that displacement in any mechanical degree of freedom always comes with some energy dissipation (damping), then the scenario on CB level at 4000 Hz oscillations may very well be that the damping strength of the PDE in a CB (‘viscously’) blocks movements in its AE, while all externally enforced strain occurs in the HS’s SE (including bending myosin heads), with the damping strength of the SDE being low enough to not mask SE elasticity. Our present model undoubtedly awaits the respective verifying simulations, however, they would go beyond the scope of this model-introducing study. This particularly holds because of what we have observed here (and preliminarily addressed in Sec. 3.1): First, impact simulations on physiological intensity level are non-distinctive with regard to whether PDE damping strength depends on either SE force or AE force, or both, whereas rapid step simulations definitely are [37]. Second, there is also some discrepancy between the PDE strength ($D_{def,max,cb}$ or $D_{hyd,max,cb}$) required to reproduce wobbling mass experiments [36, 35] versus a combination of SDE and PDE strengths ($D_{def,max,cb}$ and $D_{hyd,max,cb}$) required to reproduce rapid step experiments [38, 39, 40]. We conclude that this demands model enhancement in order to explain with one model, i.e. the same model including all parameter values, the muscle fibre responses to both these loading conditions, plus the high-frequency responses found in [41], and potentially also the damped wave propagation hypothesised in [1, 3, 2].

The model value $K_{AE,ref,max} \approx 4000 \text{ Nm}^{-1}$ (in fact, $c_{3,cb} = 1 \text{ nm}$ is the determinative model parameter) we have found for the overall AE ‘stiffness’ of the rat belly (length: 33 mm) to allow well reproducing measured fibre strains [35, fig. 5] is close to what was found (“short range stiffness” $K_{cat,sol} \approx 9000 \text{ Nm}^{-1}$ [63, p. 337]) fifty years ago in experiments [63] in which an intact, in-situ cat *m. soleus* was exposed to 11 Hz length oscillations of 0.2 mm amplitude [63, fig. 2c] (i.e. 0.6% strain, given fibre length of about 30mm [62, fig. 2]). Note that the tendons of this cat muscle are very short (therefore also very stiff), thus, their actually measured MTC stiffness values can be assumed to represent fibre stiffness well. Their fibre stiffness value being higher than our AE ‘stiffness’ can be easily explained by four factors. (i) Mass inertia augments externally measurable force resistance upon induced oscillations, as (ii) does any damping in the AE (PDE), as well as (iii) a PEE, which is (a) very likely to be in effect at AE elongations already slightly above a CB’s reference position, while (b) the cat HSs in the experiments [63] were indeed usually slightly over-stretched [62, fig. 2]. Fourth (iv), it is very likely in real muscles that their CB positions are statistically distributed, i.e. part of their ensemble is closer to the state ‘end of work stroke’, where the slope of our model AE’s force-length relation is steeper than at the AE’s reference position. This again augments the average (measured) fibre stiffness.

As a last note, a recent study [56] suggested an enhancement of Hill-type muscle models by separating, within the CE’s force-length relation, force responses to “long range” length disturbances compensated by corresponding stiffness values from those to a range of “small” perturbations compensated by higher stiffness values. Furthermore, “small” [71] were distinguished from “short range” [63] perturbations, with “small” meaning fibre strains in the range 1-4% [56, app. 9, note 1], and (visco-)elasticity in the “small” regime being in-between (lower) “long range stiffness” and (higher) “short range stiffness”. As we have just outlined, the latter is simply due to what we have implemented in our present model as the slope of the AE force-length relation. Hence, the separate modelling of CE force-length (plus dissipative) properties for the “small” perturbation range in their [56] enhanced Hill-type model does still not capture the mechanical resistance by non-disrupted CBs. To turn the argument around, forcible disruption of CBs very likely attends to “small perturbations”, with the corresponding ‘protein friction’ [64, 65, 66, 67, 68, 69, 70] also very likely causing a higher dissipative power than what we have implemented as a PDE (and SDE) in our present CB-CE model.

5. Conclusion

Letting dynamically interact a muscle’s own distributed mass with our present mechanical CB-CE model, which is based on a CB’s structure that well contains in itself the Hill relation [37, 72, 73], and combining these two structural model ingredients with macroscopic mechanical modelling of e.g. aponeuroses [74, 75, 76], tendons [77, 42, 78, 79], pennation [74, 80, 81], diverse belly shapes [81], and their changes with length [82] as with external (contact) forces [83, 84, 85], is a promising ansatz on which to build enhanced models of muscle contraction that additionally capture CB cycling processes (attachment-detachment-reattachment) [86, 87, 88, 89, 90, 91, 92, 93, 94, 95, 96, 97] based on thermodynamics; to this end, recent marvellous reviews by C.J. Barclay, N.A. Curtin, and R.C. Woledge [96, 98, 99, 100, 101] on the empirical knowledge of CB cycling energetics will be our guide.

767 Competing interests

768 We have no conflicts of interest.

769 Funding

770 This work was funded by the “Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft” (DFG) grants SI841/7-3, and SCHM2392/5-3
771 (project number: 234087184) to Tobias Siebert and Syn Schmitt, respectively.

772 References

- 773 [1] T. Blangé, J. M. Karemaker, A. E. J. L. Kramer, Tension transients after quick release in rat and frog skeletal
774 muscles, *Nature* 237 (5353) (1972) 281–282.
- 775 [2] G. J. M. Stienen, T. Blangé, Tension responses to rapid length changes in skinned muscle fibres of the frog,
776 *Pflügers Archiv – European Journal of Physiology* 405 (1) (1985) 5–11.
- 777 [3] T. Blangé, G. J. M. Stienen, Transmission phenomena and early tension recovery in skinned muscle fibres of
778 the frog, *Pflügers Archiv – European Journal of Physiology* 405 (1) (1985) 12–18.
- 779 [4] S. Schmitt, M. Günther, Human leg impact: energy dissipation of wobbling masses, *Archive of Applied Me-*
780 *chanics* 81 (7) (2011) 887–897. doi:10.1007/s00419-010-0458-z.
- 781 [5] J. Denoth, K. Gruber, M. Keppler, H. Ruder, Forces and torques during sport activities with high accelera-
782 tions, in: S. Perren, E. Schneider (Eds.), *Biomechanics: Current Interdisciplinary Research, Developments in*
783 *Biomechanics*, Springer Netherlands, 1985, pp. 663–668.
- 784 [6] K. Gruber, H. Ruder, J. Denoth, K. Schneider, A comparative study of impact dynamics: wobbling mass model
785 versus rigid body models, *Journal of Biomechanics* 31 (5) (1998) 439–444.
- 786 [7] W. Liu, B. M. Nigg, A mechanical model to determine the influence of masses and mass distribution on the
787 impact force during running, *Journal of Biomechanics* 33 (2) (2000) 219–224.
- 788 [8] M. T. G. Pain, J. H. Challis, The role of the heel pad and shank soft tissue during impacts: a further resolution
789 of a paradox, *Journal of Biomechanics* 34 (3) (2001) 327–333.
- 790 [9] M. T. G. Pain, J. H. Challis, Wobbling mass influence on impact ground reaction forces: a simulation model
791 sensitivity analysis, *Journal of Applied Biomechanics* 20 (3) (2004) 309–316.
- 792 [10] M. T. G. Pain, J. H. Challis, The influence of soft tissue movement on ground reaction forces, joint torques
793 and reaction forces in drop landings, *Journal of Biomechanics* 39 (1) (2006) 119–124.
- 794 [11] M. J. R. Gittoes, M. A. Brewin, D. G. Kerwin, Soft tissue contributions to impact forces simulated using a
795 four-segment wobbling mass model of forefoot-heel landings, *Human Movement Science* 25 (6) (2006) 775–787.
- 796 [12] A. A. Zadpoor, A. A. Nikooyan, A mechanical model to determine the influence of masses and mass distribution
797 on the impact force during running – A discussion, *Journal of Biomechanics* 39 (2) (2006) 388–390, Letter to
798 the Editor.
- 799 [13] A. A. Zadpoor, A. A. Nikooyan, A. R. Arshi, A model-based parametric study of impact force during running,
800 *Journal of Biomechanics* 40 (9) (2007) 2012–2021.
- 801 [14] C. Mills, M. T. G. Pain, M. R. Yeadon, The influence of simulation model complexity on the estimation of
802 internal loading in gymnastics landings, *Journal of Biomechanics* 41 (3) (2008) 620–628.
- 803 [15] J. Wakeling, B. Nigg, Soft-tissue vibrations in the quadriceps measured with skin mounted transducers, *Journal*
804 *of Biomechanics* 34 (4) (2001) 539–543.
- 805 [16] M. T. G. Pain, J. H. Challis, Soft tissue motion during impacts: their potential contribution to energy dissipa-
806 tion, *Journal of Applied Biomechanics* 18 (3) (2002) 231–242.

- [17] J. Wakeling, B. Nigg, Modification of soft tissue vibrations in the leg by muscular activity, *Journal of Applied Physiology* 90 (2) (2001) 412–420.
- [18] J. Wakeling, B. Nigg, A. Rozitis, Muscle activity damps the soft tissue resonance that occurs in response to pulsed and continuous vibrations, *Journal of Applied Physiology* 93 (3) (2002) 1093–1103.
- [19] J. Wakeling, A.-M. Liphardt, B. Nigg, Muscle activity reduces soft-tissue resonance at heel-strike during walking, *Journal of Biomechanics* 36 (12) (2003) 1761–1769.
- [20] K. A. Boyer, B. M. Nigg, Soft tissue vibrations within one soft tissue compartment, *Journal of Biomechanics* 39 (4) (2006) 645–651.
- [21] K. A. Boyer, B. M. Nigg, Quantification of the input signal for soft tissue vibration during running, *Journal of Biomechanics* 40 (8) (2007) 1877–1880.
- [22] M. Günther, V. A. Sholukha, D. Keßler, V. Wank, R. Blickhan, Dealing with skin motion and wobbling masses in inverse dynamics, *Journal of Mechanics in Medicine and Biology* 3 (3/4) (2003) 309–335. doi:10.1142/S0219519403000831.
- [23] M. Günther, R. Rockenfeller, T. Weihmann, D. F. B. Haeufle, T. Götz, S. Schmitt, Rules of nature’s *Formula Run*: Muscle mechanics during late stance is the key to explaining maximum running speed, *Journal of Theoretical Biology* 523 (2021) 110714. doi:10.1016/j.jtbi.2021.110714.
- [24] D. Labonte, A theory of physiological similarity in muscle-driven motion, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the USA* 120 (24) (2023) e2221217120. doi:10.1073/pnas.2221217120.
- [25] D. Labonte, P. Bishop, T. Dick, C. Clemente, Dynamic similarity and the peculiar allometry of maximum running speed, *Nature Communications* 15 (2024) 2181. doi:10.1038/s41467-024-46269-w.
- [26] D. Labonte, N. C. Holt, Beyond power limits: the kinetic energy capacity of skeletal muscle, *The Journal of Experimental Biology* 227 (Pt 21) (2024) jeb.247150. doi:10.1242/jeb.247150.
- [27] M. Günther, D. F. B. Haeufle, O. Röhrle, S. Schmitt, Spreading out muscle mass within a Hill-type model: a computer simulation study, *Computational and Mathematical Methods in Medicine* (2012) 848630 (13pp). doi:10.1155/2012/848630.
- [28] A. V. Hill, The heat of shortening and the dynamic constants of muscle, *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London B* 126 (1938) 136–195.
- [29] S. A. Ross, J. M. Wakeling, Muscle shortening velocity depends on tissue inertia and level of activation during submaximal contractions, *Biology Letters* 12 (6) (2016) 20151041.
- [30] S. A. Ross, N. Nigam, J. M. Wakeling, A modelling approach for exploring muscle dynamics during cyclic contractions, *PLoS Computational Biology* 14 (4) (2018) e1006123.
- [31] S. A. Ross, B. Rimkus, N. Konow, A. A. Biewener, J. M. Wakeling, Added mass in rat plantaris muscle causes a reduction in mechanical work, *The Journal of Experimental Biology* 223 (Pt 19) (2020) jeb224410.
- [32] S. A. Ross, J. M. Wakeling, The energy of muscle contraction. IV. Greater mass of larger muscles decreases contraction efficiency, *Journal of the Royal Society Interface* 18 (182) (2021) 20210484.
- [33] J. L. van Leeuwen, W. M. Kier, Functional design of tentacles in squid: linking sarcomere ultrastructure to gross morphological dynamics, *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London B* 352 (1353) (1997) 551–571.
- [34] K. B. Christensen, M. Günther, S. Schmitt, T. Siebert, Muscle wobbling mass dynamics: eigenfrequency dependencies on activity, impact strength, and ground material, *Scientific Reports* 13 (2023) 19575 (12pp). doi:10.1038/s41598-023-45821-w.

- 848 [35] K. B. Christensen, M. Günther, S. Schmitt, T. Siebert, Strain in shock-loaded skeletal muscle and the
849 time scale of muscular wobbling mass dynamics, *Scientific Reports* 7 (2017) 13266 (11pp). doi:10.1038/
850 s41598-017-13630-7.
- 851 [36] K. B. Christensen, M. Günther, S. Schmitt, T. Siebert, Cross-bridge mechanics estimated from skeletal muscles'
852 work-loop responses to impacts in legged locomotion, *Scientific Reports* 11 (2021) 23638 (12pp). doi:10.1038/
853 s41598-021-02819-6.
- 854 [37] M. Günther, D. F. B. Haeufle, S. Schmitt, The basic mechanical structure of the skeletal muscle machinery:
855 one model for linking microscopic and macroscopic scales, *Journal of Theoretical Biology* 456 (2018) 137–167.
856 doi:10.1016/j.jtbi.2018.07.023.
- 857 [38] L. E. Ford, A. F. Huxley, R. M. Simmons, Tension responses to sudden length change in stimulated frog muscle
858 fibres near slack length, *The Journal of Physiology* 269 (2) (1977) 441–515.
- 859 [39] G. Piazzesi, V. Lombardi, A cross-bridge model that is able to explain mechanical and energetic properties of
860 shortening muscle, *Biophysical Journal* 68 (5) (1995) 1966–1979.
- 861 [40] G. Piazzesi, L. Lucii, V. Lombardi, The size and the speed of the working stroke of muscle myosin and its
862 dependence on the force, *The Journal of Physiology* 545 (Pt 1) (2002) 145–151.
- 863 [41] L. Fusi, E. Brunello, M. Reconditi, G. Piazzesi, V. Lombardi, The non-linear elasticity of the muscle sarcomere
864 and the compliance of myosin motors, *The Journal of Physiology* 592 (Pt 5) (2014) 1109–1118.
- 865 [42] M. Günther, S. Schmitt, V. Wank, High-frequency oscillations as a consequence of neglected serial damping in
866 Hill-type muscle models, *Biological Cybernetics* 97 (1) (2007) 63–79. doi:10.1007/s00422-007-0160-6.
- 867 [43] K. C. Holmes, The swinging lever-arm hypothesis of muscle contraction, *Current Biology* 7 (2) (1997) R112–
868 R118. doi:10.1016/s0960-9822(06)00051-0.
- 869 [44] K. C. Holmes, M. A. Geeves, The structural basis of muscle contraction, *Philosophical Transactions of the*
870 *Royal Society of London B* 355 (1396) (2000) 419–431. doi:10.1098/rstb.2000.0583.
- 871 [45] M. J. Lampinen, T. Noponen, Electric dipole theory and thermodynamics of actomyosin molecular motor in
872 muscle contraction, *Journal of Theoretical Biology* 236 (4) (2005) 397–421. doi:10.1016/j.jtbi.2005.03.020.
- 873 [46] E. V. Rosenfeld, The interrelation between mechanical characteristics of contracting muscle, cross-bridge in-
874 ternal structure, and the mechanism of chemomechanical energy transduction, *European Biophysics Journal*
875 41 (9) (2012) 733–753.
- 876 [47] E. V. Rosenfeld, M. Günther, An enhanced model of cross-bridge operation with internal elasticity, *European*
877 *Biophysics Journal* 43 (4-5) (2014) 131–141. doi:10.1007/s00249-014-0947-z.
- 878 [48] M. Krieg, Simulation und Steuerung biomechanischer Mehrkörpersysteme, Master's thesis, Eberhard-Karls-
879 Universität, Tübingen, Germany, [in German:] [https://biomechanicsbiorobotics.info/tatbiomechanik/
880 publ/dipl/michaelkrieg/diplom_michael_krieg.pdf](https://biomechanicsbiorobotics.info/tatbiomechanik/publ/dipl/michaelkrieg/diplom_michael_krieg.pdf) (1992).
- 881 [49] U. Hahn, Entwicklung mehrgliedriger Modelle zur realistischen Simulation dynamischer Prozesse in biolo-
882 gischen Systemen, Master's thesis, Eberhard-Karls-Universität, Tübingen, Germany, [in German:] [https://
883 //biomechanicsbiorobotics.info/tatbiomechanik/publ/dipl/ulihahn/diplom_uli_hahn.pdf](https://biomechanicsbiorobotics.info/tatbiomechanik/publ/dipl/ulihahn/diplom_uli_hahn.pdf) (1993).
- 884 [50] M. Günther, H. Ruder, Synthesis of two-dimensional human walking: a test of the λ -model, *Biological Cyber-*
885 *netics* 89 (2) (2003) 89–106. doi:10.1007/s00422-003-0414-x.
- 886 [51] M. Günther, H. Wagner, Dynamics of quiet human stance: computer simulations of a triple inverted pendulum
887 model, *Computer Methods in Biomechanics and Biomedical Engineering* 19 (8) (2016) 819–834. doi:10.1080/
888 10255842.2015.1067306.
- 889 [52] L. F. Shampine, M. K. Gordon, *Computer Solution of Ordinary Differential Equations: The Initial Value*
890 *Problem*, W.H. Freeman & Co., San Francisco, 1975.

- [53] R. Rockenfeller, M. Günther, N. Stutzig, D. F. B. Haeufle, T. Siebert, S. Schmitt, K. Leichsenring, M. Böl, T. Götz, Exhaustion of skeletal muscle fibers within seconds: incorporating phosphate kinetics into a Hill-type model, *Frontiers in Physiology* 11 (2020) 306 (25pp). doi:10.3389/fphys.2020.00306.
- [54] C. Rode, T. Siebert, R. Blickhan, Titin-induced force enhancement and force depression: A 'sticky-spring' mechanism in muscle contractions?, *Journal of Theoretical Biology* 259 (2) (2009) 350–360.
- [55] G. Schappacher-Tilp, T. Leonard, G. Desch, W. Herzog, A novel three-filament model of force generation in eccentric contraction of skeletal muscles, *PLoS One* 10 (3) (2015) e0117634.
- [56] M. Millard, D. W. Franklin, W. Herzog, A three filament mechanistic model of musculotendon force and impedance, *eLife* 12 (2023) RP88344, final "Version of Record published 10 September 2024". doi:10.7554/eLife.88344.
- [57] R. J. Podolsky, Kinetics of muscular contraction: the approach to the steady state, *Nature* 188 (4751) (1960) 666–668.
- [58] M. M. Civan, R. J. Podolsky, Contraction kinetics of striated muscle fibres following quick changes in load, *The Journal of Physiology* 184 (1966) 511–534.
- [59] M. Reconditi, M. Linari, L. Lucii, A. Stewart, Y. B. Sun, P. Boesecke, T. Narayanan, R. F. Fischetti, T. C. Irving, G. Piazzesi, M. Irving, V. Lombardi, The myosin motor in muscle generates a smaller and slower working stroke at higher load, *Nature* 428 (6982) (2004) 578–581.
- [60] D. C. Bickham, T. G. West, M. R. Webb, R. C. Woledge, N. A. Curtin, M. A. Ferenczi, Millisecond-scale biochemical response to change in strain, *Biophysical Journal* 101 (10) (2011) 2445–2454.
- [61] M. A. Geeves, K. C. Holmes, Structural mechanism of muscle contraction, *Annual Review of Biochemistry* 68 (1999) 687–728.
- [62] P. M. H. Rack, D. R. Westbury, The effects of length and stimulus rate on tension in the isometric cat soleus muscle, *The Journal of Physiology* 204 (2) (1969) 443–460.
- [63] P. M. H. Rack, D. R. Westbury, The short range stiffness of active mammalian muscle and its effect on mechanical properties, *The Journal of Physiology* 240 (2) (1974) 331–350.
- [64] K. Tawada, K. Sekimoto, Protein friction exerted by motor enzymes through a weak-binding interaction, *Journal of Theoretical Biology* 150 (2) (1991) 193–200.
- [65] K. Tawada, K. Sekimoto, A physical model of ATP-induced actin-myosin movement in vitro, *Biophysical Journal* 59 (2) (1991) 343–356.
- [66] M. E. Fisher, A. B. Kolomeisky, The force exerted by a molecular motor, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the USA* 96 (12) (1999) 6597–6602.
- [67] A. Parmeggiani, F. Jülicher, A. Ajdari, J. Prost, Energy transduction of isothermal ratchets: generic aspects and specific examples close to and far from equilibrium, *Physical Review E* 60 (2 Pt B) (1999) 2127–2140.
- [68] H. Suda, Origin of friction derived from rupture dynamics, *Langmuir* 17 (20) (2001) 6045–6047.
- [69] V. Bormuth, V. Varga, J. Howard, E. Schäffer, Protein friction limits diffusive and directed movements of kinesin motors on microtubules, *Science* 325 (5942) (2009) 870–873.
- [70] C. Veigel, C. F. Schmidt, Friction in motor proteins, *Science* 325 (5942) (2009) 826–827.
- [71] R. F. Kirsch, D. Boskov, W. Z. Rymer, Muscle stiffness during transient and continuous movements of cat muscle: perturbation characteristics and physiological relevance, *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering* BME-41 (8) (1994) 758–770.
- [72] M. Günther, S. Schmitt, A macroscopic ansatz to deduce the Hill relation, *Journal of Theoretical Biology* 263 (4) (2010) 407–418. doi:10.1016/j.jtbi.2009.12.027.

- 933 [73] C. Y. Seow, Hill's equation of muscle performance and its hidden insight on molecular mechanisms, *The Journal*
934 *of General Physiology* 142 (6) (2013) 561–573.
- 935 [74] C. J. Zuurbier, P. A. Huijing, Influence of muscle geometry on shortening speed of fibre, aponeurosis and
936 muscle, *Journal of Biomechanics* 25 (9) (1992) 1017–1026.
- 937 [75] E. Azizi, T. J. Roberts, Biaxial strain and variable stiffness in aponeuroses, *The Journal of Physiology* 587 (Pt
938 17) (2009) 4309–4318.
- 939 [76] B. J. Raiteri, Aponeurosis behaviour during muscular contraction: A narrative review, *European Journal of*
940 *Sports Science* 18 (8) (2018) 1128–1138. doi:10.1080/17461391.2018.1472299.
- 941 [77] C. M. Pollock, R. E. Shadwick, Relationship between body mass and biomechanical properties of limb tendons
942 in adult mammals, *American Journal of Physiology* 266 (3 Pt 2) (1994) R1016–1021.
- 943 [78] M. Bontempi, Probabilistic model of ligaments and tendons: Quasistatic linear stretching, *Physical Review E*
944 79 (3) (2010) 030903(R). doi:10.1103/PhysRevE.79.030903.
- 945 [79] Z. Guo, R. De Vita, Probabilistic constitutive law for damage in ligaments, *Medical Engineering & Physics*
946 31 (9) (2009) 1104–1109. doi:10.1016/j.medengphy.2009.06.011.
- 947 [80] C. J. Zuurbier, P. A. Huijing, Changes in geometry of actively shortening unipennate rat gastrocnemius muscle,
948 *Journal of Morphology* 218 (2) (1993) 167–180.
- 949 [81] R. Rockenfeller, M. Günther, C. J. Clemente, T. J. M. Dick, Rethinking the physiological cross-sectional area
950 of skeletal muscle reveals the mechanical advantage of pennation, *Royal Society Open Science* 11 (9) (2024)
951 240037. doi:10.1098/rsos.240037.
- 952 [82] E. Azizi, E. L. Brainerd, T. J. Roberts, Variable gearing in pennate muscles, *Proceedings of the National*
953 *Academy of Sciences of the USA* 105 (5) (2008) 1745–1750.
- 954 [83] T. Siebert, M. Günther, R. Blickhan, A 3D-geometric model for the deformation of a transversally loaded
955 muscle, *Journal of Theoretical Biology* 298 (2012) 116–121. doi:10.1016/j.jtbi.2012.01.009.
- 956 [84] T. Siebert, O. Till, R. Blickhan, Work partitioning of transversally loaded muscle: experimentation and
957 simulation, *Computer Methods in Biomechanics and Biomedical Engineering* 17 (3) (2014) 217–229. doi:
958 10.1080/10255842.2012.675056.
- 959 [85] T. Siebert, O. Till, N. Stutzig, M. Günther, R. Blickhan, Muscle force depends on the amount of transversal
960 muscle loading, *Journal of Biomechanics* 47 (8) (2014) 1822–1828. doi:10.1016/j.jbiomech.2014.03.029.
- 961 [86] A. F. Huxley, Muscle structure and theories of contraction, *Progress in Biophysics and Biophysical Chemistry*
962 7 (1957) 255–318.
- 963 [87] A. F. Huxley, A note suggesting that the cross-bridge attachment during muscle contraction may take place in
964 two stages, *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London B* 183 (1973) 83–86.
- 965 [88] G. I. Zahalak, S. Ma, Muscle activation and contraction: constitutive relations based directly on cross-bridge
966 kinetics, *Journal of Biomechanical Engineering* 112 (1) (1990) 52–62.
- 967 [89] K. K. Lemaire, G. C. Baan, R. T. Jaspers, A. van Soest, Comparison of the validity of Hill and Huxley
968 muscle-tendon complex models using experimental data obtained from rat m. soleus *in situ*, *The Journal of*
969 *Experimental Biology* 219 (Pt 7) (2016) 977–987.
- 970 [90] A. van Soest, L. J. R. Casius, K. K. Lemaire, Huxley-type cross-bridge models in largeish-scale musculoskeletal
971 models; an evaluation of computational cost, *Journal of Biomechanics* 83 (1) (2019) 43–48. doi:10.1016/j.
972 jbiomech.2018.11.021.
- 973 [91] R. C. Woledge, N. A. Curtin, E. Homsher, Energetic Aspects of Muscle Contraction, in: *Monographs of the*
974 *Physiological Society* 41, Academic Press, London, 1985, pp. 1–357.

- 975 [92] V. Lombardi, G. Piazzesi, M. Linari, Rapid regeneration of the actin-myosin power stroke in contracting muscle,
976 Nature 355 (6361) (1992) 638–641.
- 977 [93] V. Lombardi, G. Piazzesi, M. A. Ferenczi, H. Thirlwell, I. Dobbie, M. Irving, Elastic distortion of myosin heads
978 and repriming of the working stroke in muscle, Nature 374 (6522) (1995) 553–555.
- 979 [94] K. Hirose, C. Franzini-Armstrong, Y. E. Goldman, J. M. Murray, Structural changes in muscle crossbridges
980 accompanying force generation, The Journal of Cell Biology 127 (3) (1994) 763–778.
- 981 [95] R. T. Tregear, M. C. Reedy, Y. E. Goldman, K. A. Taylor, H. Winkler, C. Franzini-Armstrong, H. Sasaki, C. Lu-
982 caveche, M. K. Reedy, Cross-bridge number, position, and angle in target zones of cryofixed isometrically active
983 insect flight muscle, Biophysical Journal 86 (5) (2004) 3009–3019. doi:10.1016/S0006-3495(04)74350-7.
- 984 [96] C. J. Barclay, R. C. Woledge, N. A. Curtin, Inferring crossbridge properties from skeletal muscle energetics,
985 Progress in Biophysics and Molecular Biology 102 (1) (2010) 53–71.
- 986 [97] C. J. Barclay, Energy demand and supply in human skeletal muscle, Journal of Muscle Research and Cell
987 Motility 38 (2) (2017) 143–155.
- 988 [98] C. J. Barclay, Energetics of contraction, Comprehensive Physiology 5 (2) (2015) 961–995.
- 989 [99] C. J. Barclay, A century of exercise physiology: key concepts in muscle energetics, European Journal of Applied
990 Physiology 123 (1) (2023) 25–42. doi:10.1007/s00421-022-05070-7.
- 991 [100] C. J. Barclay, N. A. Curtin, Advances in understanding the energetics of muscle contraction, Journal of Biome-
992 chanics 156 (2023) 111669. doi:10.1016/j.jbiomech.2023.111669.
- 993 [101] N. A. Curtin, C. J. Barclay, The energetics of muscle contractions resembling *in vivo* performance, Journal of
994 Biomechanics 156 (2023) 111665. doi:10.1016/j.jbiomech.2023.111665.

Figure 1:

Experimental setup for determining an MTC's mechanical response to its suspending frame impacting the ground.

The simulated MTC model structure is sketched by the rightmost chain of $n_{PM} = n_{CE} + 1 = 25$ PMs (red blobs), plus the chain's distal and proximal TACs (yellow curly threads) with their bone attachment remainders clamped to the frame (grey C-shape); each one of the $n_{CE} = 24$ modelled contractile element (CEs; length of CE, i : $L_{CE,i}$) connects two adjacent PMs in the chain; in the present model, each PM has in fact only one mechanical degree of freedom (DoF), because the MTC is oriented vertically (y -direction), and the CoMs of MTC and frame, as well as both the frame's contact point with the ground (cushion, green) and the frame's rail on the stand (black L-shape) all align with gravitational acceleration directed in y -direction; thus, all forces and the resulting kinematics have only non-vanishing y -components, no torques occur, the model is accordingly one-dimensional (Eqs. (1,6)); note that the overall (optimal) MTC length is 4.5 cm (mass $\mathcal{M} = 2$ g), while the real frame's height is 12 cm (mass $\mathcal{M}_{fra} = 52$ g), whereas we have left out sketching the add-ons (like the force sensor and the insulators [35, fig. 1]) connecting the frame's cantilevers with the clamps.

Leftmost, an enlarged sketch of the general structure of our muscle model is shown: one (representative) CB connecting two PMs. For the transfer of the CB structure to a mechanical arrangement of ('rheological') sub-elements of a CE, i , see Fig.3, and for model element scaling from the microscopic structure of a CB via a HS to one CE, i (see Fig.5).

Figure 2:

1009 Mass distribution of the 25 PMs versus their initial position in the vertical direction (y).
 1010 Overall mass is $\mathcal{M} = 2$ g; anatomical centre of muscle belly at 0.0 cm; negative means distal.

Figure 3:

The model of muscle fibre force generation: a mechanistic, reductionist model of the CB structure (top, left), a visualisation of a transformation of this model idea into a mechanical model arrangement of ‘rheological’ elements AE, SE, PDE, and SDE (top, right), the latter model sketched for approximately the condition ‘end of work stroke’ (bottom, left), as well as the force-length relations (bottom, right) of the two crucial CB model elements AE (drive of CB, source of energy) and SE (elastic transmission in series to AE).

This CB model of ‘rheological’ elements is homogeneously expanded by $1 \leq n_{hs,cb} \leq n_{hs,cbmax}$ to a HS, as implied by sketching only one (representative) model CB connecting Z-disc and M-line (top, right and bottom, left): All of the $n_{hs,cb}$ CBs in a HS are attached to the same (myosin and actin) filaments, and they contribute to HS stiffness (i.e. act on the same structural SE part; $K_{SE,hs,fil}$) with both their AE compliances (slope of force-length relation) and their elastic SE parts ($K_{SE,cb}$); the model’s SE part is therefore already indicated by ‘hs’; all CBs are assumed to act synchronously in our model, i.e. are attached in the same AE state, sharing the same length coordinate $L_{AE,cb}$ of their drives (therefore indicated by ‘cb’); ‘activity’ is $u_{AE} = \frac{n_{hs,cb}}{n_{hs,cbmax}}$ (Eq. (2)).

Independent input parameters are plotted in **bold font**; basic model (default) input parameter values (Table 1) are $L_{hs,ref} = 1100$ nm, $n_{hs,cbmax} = 100$, $F_{cb,ref} = 4$ pN, $L_{AE,cb,ref} = 7$ nm, $K_{SE,cb} = 3 \frac{\text{pN}}{\text{nm}}$, $c_3 = 1$ nm, and $L_{SE,hs,cbmax} = 4$ nm; this yields maximum isometric HS force, $F_{hs,max} = n_{hs,cbmax} \cdot F_{cb,ref} = 400$ pN, work stroke length, $L_{hs,cbmax} = L_{AE,cb,ref} + L_{SE,hs,cbmax} = 11$ nm, filament contribution to SE stiffness (inferred: Eq. (30)) $K_{SE,hs,fil} = 150 \frac{\text{pN}}{\text{nm}}$, and thus $K_{SE,hs,max} = 100 \frac{\text{pN}}{\text{nm}}$ (Table 2: a HS’s SE stiffness, Eq. (28), at full activity $u_{AE} = 1$), with the latter then implying $\frac{K_{SE,hs,max}}{n_{hs,cbmax}} = 1 \frac{\text{pN}}{\text{nm}}$ as an average HS stiffness contribution per (‘representative’) CB; if just one CB is attached (lowest

activity: $u_{AE} = 0.01$), a HS’s SE stiffness $K_{SE,hs}(u_{AE} = 0.01) = 2.94 \frac{\text{pN}}{\text{nm}}$ (Table 2) practically equals a single CB’s SE stiffness $K_{SE,cb} = 3 \frac{\text{pN}}{\text{nm}}$. A ‘representative’ CB’s SE stiffness is thus threefold when compared with full activity; symbolically equating ΔL_{hs} with $\Delta L_{CE,hs}$ is for emphasising that one model HS is the basic template for any CE unit in our model.

half-sarcomere's $K_{AE,hs} / K_{SE,hs}$ vs. activity u_{AE} ; AE position: $L_{AE,cb}$

Figure 4:

Ratio $\frac{K_{AE,hs}}{K_{SE,hs}}$ of AE force-length slope and SE stiffness (see Eqs. (33) and (28)) in a HS versus activity u_{AE} .

Each curve represents the ratio's u_{AE} -dependency at a given position (length $L_{AE,cb}$) of all CBs in the HS; the value of the latter parameter is varied, with approaching from the CB's reference length $L_{AE,cb} = L_{AE,cb,ref} = 7$ nm the position 'end of work stroke' at $L_{AE,cb} = 0$; for further illustration, see also the two force-length panels Fig.3,bottom,right).

Figure 5:

Scaling from CB structure via the HS to a macroscopic CE,i; the two red-filled circles are adjacent PMs; independent input parameters are plotted in **bold font**, as printed in this caption.

Parameter values are $F_{max} = 30$ N, $F_{cb,ref} = 4$ pN, $n_{hs,cbmax} = 100$, $1 \leq n_{hs,cb} \leq n_{hs,cbmax}$, $L_{hs,ref} = 1100$ nm, $L_{CE,opt} = 33$ mm, and $n_{CE} = 24$, hence, $L_{CE,opt,i} = \frac{L_{CE,opt}}{n_{CE}} = L_{CE,opt,24}$, $n_{L,hs,i} = \frac{L_{CE,opt,i}}{L_{hs,ref}} = n_{L,hs,24}$, $F_{hs,max} = n_{hs,cbmax} \cdot F_{cb,ref}$, $n_{CSA,hs} = \frac{F_{max}}{n_{hs,cbmax} \cdot F_{cb,ref}} = \frac{F_{max}}{F_{hs,max}}$, $n_{CSA,cbmax} = n_{hs,cbmax} \cdot n_{CSA,hs} = \frac{F_{max}}{F_{cb,ref}}$, and $n_{CSA,hs} \leq n_{CSA,cb} \leq n_{CSA,cbmax}$.

The rightmost panel sketches the basic mechanical element structure that is eventually implemented as a one-internal-degree-of-freedom representation of the assembly of the serially arranged sarcomeres (i.e. HSs according to the middle panel): a CE made of a driving (conceivably by Coulomb forces) AE and a (conceivably linear elastic) SE in series, with each the AE (PDE) and the SE (SDE) being damped in parallel (PDE and SDE, respectively); a parallel elastic element (PEE) with u_{AE} -independent (constant), low stiffness (see Eq. (5) and Table 2) is implemented by default in our model.

Figure 6:

Length, i.e. stretch, signals (top, left; including pre-stretch) and stretch rates (bottom, left) of both AE and SE, the respective forces generated by the four 'rheological elements' AE, SE, PDE, and SDE (bottom, right) that make up the more proximally located belly part CE,18 (with reference length $1375.0 \mu\text{m}$), as well as fluctuations of TAC forces (top, right), i.e. the force fluctuation, in response to the impact, between the distal and proximal terminations of the model MTC.

Vertical dashed line is instant of (the frame's) TD; activity is $u_{AE} = 0.75$; right panels: forces F_{AE} and F_{SE} , as well as both TAC force fluctuations, $\Delta F_{TAC,j}$, are in fact the deviations from the isometric force $F_{CE} = 22.76 \text{ N}$ at TD (pre-load, including $F_{PEE} = 0.07 \text{ N}$); there is some discrepancy between the force fluctuation in the simulation ($\Delta F_{peak} = 0.455 \text{ N}$; top: black line with plus signs) and the experimentally determined value ($\Delta \overline{F}_{peak} = 0.34 \text{ N}$) (see caption of Fig. 7), but see comment in Sec. 3.2.2; assuming a homogeneous mass distribution in a kinematic data analysis (mass \mathcal{M} times arithmetic mean value of all accelerations of all PMs; top: yellow line with crosses), while it is not, prods to why the experimental analysis performed [36, 35] may be prone to underestimate ΔF_{peak} .

Figure 7:

Local muscle fibre strains $\delta_{CE,j}(t)$ (Eq. (39)) versus time t , in response to an impact event along the tendon (and gravity) direction (vertical). Strain values were extracted from kinematic data of GAS muscles, measured in active contraction experiments [35], in which several GAS MTC specimens had been dissected from anaesthetised animals, (vertically) suspended in a frame (compare with our simulation model, Fig. 1), spotted with markers, activated, and the suspending frame dropped on the ground. Muscle activity values u_{AE} are reported as the ratio $\frac{F_{GAS,TD}}{F_{GAS,max}}$ of the values of isometric force $F_{GAS,TD}$ at TD and average maximum isometric force $F_{GAS,max} = 30$ N, the latter determined in [35]. The coloured lines in the three sub-figures (a-c) show exemplary cases of traces of local muscle fibre strain in response to an impact: for the proximal (a), the distal (b), or nearly the entire (c) belly region; see their maximum amplitudes, and time spans to reach it, in Table 4. For the bellies' impact responses shown here, the mean value of the force fluctuation between the bony terminations of the MTC was $\Delta\bar{F}_{peak} = 0.34$ N. Data acquisition (d): At any instant, the arithmetic mean values of the vertical positions of all markers factored in within their regional range limits (marked by each the two blue, white, and red horizontal lines) are y_p , y_c , and y_d , respectively; thus, $L_{CE,p} = y_p - y_c$, $L_{CE,d} = y_c - y_d$, and $L_{CE} = y_p - y_d$; see their mean values in Table 3. The black circle in (d) is the marker identified to be nearest to the GAS's maximum anatomical cross-sectional area (ACSA), which, in all trials, is within the limits of the y_c range (illustrated with white horizontal lines). $L_{belly,0}$ (mean value: Table 3) is the length of the muscle belly at TD; it spans the region between the two horizontal, dashed lines in (d): from the insertion of the proximal GAS tendon, which stretches from the lowest part of the upper clamp (compare again the model sketch, Fig. 1) to its insertion into the (proximal aponeurosis of the) belly, to the insertion of the distal GAS (Achilles) tendon into the (distal aponeurosis of the) belly.

Figure 8:

1078 Strain in all CEs of models the $M2PM$, $M3PM$, and $M4PM$ (from left to right); pre-strain of most distal CE (CE,1) at TD subtracted for any CE,i.
 1074 Vertical dashed line: TD; activity runs from top (low: $u_{AE} = 0.1$) to bottom (maximum: $u_{AE} = 1.0$); note almost two orders of magnitude lower CE
 1075 strain in $M2PM$.

Figure 9:

1070 Strain in CEs of models the M_4PM (same as Fig. 8, right) and M_{25PM} (default parameter set: Tables 1,2), and in a proximally shifted region of CEs
 1078 of default M_{25PM} (from left to right); CE,1 pre-strain at TD subtracted.
 1079 Vertical dashed line: TD; activity runs from top (low: $u_{AE} = 0.1$) to bottom (maximum: $u_{AE} = 1.0$).

Figure 10:

1086 Strain in a proximally shifted region of CEs of default *M25PM* (left; same as Fig. 9, right), u_{AE} -dependent stiffness of PEEs (middle), and without
 1082 any PEEs (right); CE,1 pre-strain at TD subtracted.
 1083 Vertical dashed line: TD; activity runs from top (low: $u_{AE} = 0.1$) to bottom (maximum: $u_{AE} = 1.0$); in model with PEEs' u_{AE} -dependency (middle),
 1084 note doubled y -axis range for both $u_{AE} = 0.25$ and $u_{AE} = 0.1$; without PEEs (right), note even triplication for $u_{AE} = 0.1$, and further note that CBs
 1085 were still creeping from the initial condition to isometric equilibrium with $u_{AE} = 0.1, 0.25$, and 0.5 (slightly).

Figure 11:

1090 Strain in a proximally shifted region of CEs of default *M25PM* (left; same as Fig. 9, right), AE (stiffness) parameter c_3 increased by 50% (middle),
 1088 and homogeneous mass distribution (right); CE,1 pre-strain at TD subtracted.
 1089 Vertical dashed line: TD; activity runs from top (low: $u_{AE} = 0.1$) to bottom (maximum: $u_{AE} = 1.0$).